

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

Technical Report for period
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1 INTRODUCTION

CO2-SPICER project was officially launched on 1 November 2020 and its implementation has been planned for 3.5 years. It is being carried out by a consortium of 5 organisations from the Czech Republic and Norway under the leadership of Czech Geological Survey. For the purposes of this report, Project Partners’ acronyms were used (Tab. 1-1).

Tab. 1-1: Acronyms of Project Partners used in the report

Project Partner	Acronym
Czech Geological Survey	CGS
MND a.s.	MND
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS	NORCE
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	VSB
Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences	GFU

The project is divided into 10 Work Packages (Fig. 1-1). Each Work Package has its clearly defined leader, objectives, description of work and results. Work packages are structured into Tasks, each with a defined Task leader.

Fig. 1-1: Project structure of CO2-SPICER

The work in the 1st project period was fully oriented to the achievement of the main project objective – preparation of a pilot CO₂ storage project at the Zar-3 field in SE Czech Republic. The first important steps in this direction have been made.

The work was governed by the detailed work plan described in the document “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages” (attachment 5 to project application). Chapter 2 of this report follows the defined project structure and describes the work progress in each Work Package and Task in detail.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 WORK PACKAGE 1 – Data gathering and consolidation

Summary

The main goal of WP1 is to obtain suitable data for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site. These data sources are used as inputs during the development of a three-dimensional static geological model of the storage site and complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and monitoring (WP7). The required data have been obtained from both publicly available sources (in particular CGS database) and the archive and databases of the industrial Project Partners (and current Zar-3 field operator) MND. All collected data are consolidated and unified (Task 1.1). Task 1.2 is reserved for collection and analysis of well cores. The overview of all collected data is kept using a dedicated project geodatabase and GIS (Task 1.3).

The work in WP1 started in November 2020 and was carried out by CGS (WP leader) and MND according to the plan; some issues were caused by a tornado, which destroyed the MND core repository in Lužice in June 2021.

Task 1.1 – Collection, consolidation and unification of existing data, site characterization

The existing (geographical, geological, geophysical etc.) data gathered in frame of Task 1.1 were prepared and used as the main inputs for the development of the static geological model (WP2) and other project activities in WP6 and WP7. The following maps and data sets have been prepared:

- administrative structure of the site area and its vicinity (zoning map);
- topography and geomorphology maps (incl. digital elevation model and ortho-photo data);
- soil maps and land use maps, incl. map of identified landslides;
- hydrology and hydrogeology maps, incl. drinking water protected zones - see Fig. 2.1-1;
- map of nature protection areas;
- map of protected and safety zones for linear constructions;
- surface geology map (Carpathian Flysch Belt units);
- surface geophysics maps (gravity survey, magnetic survey, gamma ray measurement, 2D seismic lines + 3D seismic survey areas);
- deep wells identification (incl. well trajectories);
- well logs in LAS format + check-shot surveys (velocity data);
- list of shallow hydrological and engineering-geology wells.

Most of the maps listed above will also be part of the project result TO01000112-V3 (Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site; type N_{map}) that is planned to be submitted in 2023.

The Gauss-Krueger (S42, zone 3) coordinates were agreed to be used as the main coordinate system in the project.

Fig. 2.1-1: Hydrogeology map of Zar-3 area. QC I - III = quality category of groundwater (I suitable, II possible, III unsuitable as drinking water source), Q = quaternary sediments, P = Paleogene sediments, red-marked areas 1, 2a, 2b = drinking water protected areas, blue triangles = groundwater monitoring points, HV-5, HV-7 = drinking water sources (wells)

The most important sources of available geological data include information from existing wells (see also Task 1.2) and historical geological survey reports. The area of the Zar-3 reservoir (and surrounding) comprises a total of 22 deep wells; 14 of them penetrated the reservoir itself; four of them are side-tracks. Most of the wells are deviated or horizontal. In addition, about 30 shallow hydro- or engineering-geology wells were drilled in the area of interest, with different amounts of available documentation. Shallow wells represent input for shallow groundwater monitoring (WP7) while the deep wells have been used for construction of the geological model (WP2). All available valuable deep-well data were compiled and quality-checked, and put into a user-friendly format in both graphic and table forms.

Seismic data (especially 3D seismic) represent the key piece of information and data source for the development of the 3D geological model (WP2). Time and depth sections along seismic reflection profiles (2D seismic) in the site area have been retrieved from CGS geophysical database and their original geological interpretation was evaluated and updated to the current level of knowledge. The data and their interpretation were prepared for import into the 3D geological model (WP2). Project Partner MND provided the project team with three-dimensional (3D) seismic data for the Zar-3 field and surrounding area. The use of these data is covered by a Non-disclosure agreement between MND and other Project Partners. The data block covers the whole site area and its vicinity, allowing

the project team to prepare a detailed fault and structural plan of the net storage itself, as well as the whole storage complex (storage site and surrounding area in sense of valid legislation). The main interpretation work is ongoing directly in the 3D modelling environment within Task 2.1 in WP2.

Fig. 2.1-2: Example of graphic representation of well-log curves (well UH9)

Well-log data are available for 18 wells at the Zar-3 field and its vicinity; the minimum extent of used methods is resistivity, spontaneous polarization and gamma-ray logs at older wells but more complex logging is available for the younger ones. Check-shot surveys have been registered in 3 wells. All well-log records were provided by MND in digital form, mostly in the LAS format. After a quality check the data have been

visualized in a user-friendly graphic form (see Fig. 2.1-2) and provided to the project team. In addition, all well-log curves have been processed into a consolidated data file to be:

- directly imported into the modelling tools for the 3D geological model (WP2);
- used for subsequent interpretation, including, in particular, porosity and clay content calculations, which will serve as input for distribution of reservoir properties in the 3D model (WP2).

Digital data of the complete Bouguer anomalies (gravity anomalies) and ΔT or ΔZ values (geomagnetic anomalies) have been retrieved from CGS databases for the entire are of interest, , and primary contour maps have been created. These have been correlated with geological maps (1:50,000) to extend information on the sedimentary rocks from deep wells, physical rock properties (well data), sedimentary infill properties (density, magnetic susceptibility and their changes with respect to depth) and the thickness of sedimentary rocks. Unfortunately, due to insufficient quality of geomagnetic data, only sources of gravity anomalies could have been identified.

A special data source is represented by the so called “mudlog”, i.e. analysis of drill cuttings separated from the drilling mud. These data have been collected in graphic form for all reservoir wells and have been summarized in a partial database. These data provide very good information about lithology along the borehole. From the original well and Geoservice final reports, some technical drilling parameters, like weight on bit (WOB), rotation of drilling bit, velocity of drilling (min/m, m/h), pressure and true vertical depth were evaluated for each reservoir well (excluding ZA1). Such data are especially valuable for geomechanical assessment of rocks building the storage complex (WP4). Temperature and pressure history (2001 - 2021) data are available only from the well ZA3. These data provide basis for heat flow modelling and temperature distribution in dynamic modelling (WP3).

Data on oil and gas shows, pumping test results, drill stem test (“tester”) have been compiled from the archival reports and a specialized database part has been prepared for WP5 – geochemistry.

Well design data (casing, perforation, cement plugs) have been prepared as a basis for risk evaluation (WP6) for all 18 deep wells. For abandoned wells, the well design after abandonment has been compiled, including graphic representation (see Fig. 2.1-3). A special borehole measurement known as “cement log” (sonic logging focused on presence and thickness of annular cement) represents another data source for risk assessment and evaluation.

A basic site characterization is ongoing with the purpose to gather and process the main geographical and geological data on the storage site (result R1.2, March 2022). In doing so, the CGS team is using publicly available and departmental maps, maps of protected areas, data from CGS Geofond databases, as well as data from MND archives. In addition, data in the possession of organizations founded by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic are included. A field survey comprising basic geological, geographical and pedological (soil) mapping has been performed. All produced maps will be integrated – together with other thematic site maps created in other Work Packages - in the result TO01000112-V3 (type N_{map} , December 2023).

The data described above, together with all additional data gathered, measured or otherwise established in the course of the project, are stored in the project geodatabase (a spatial geodatabase in which geographical and spatial information are stored for future

reference) that is created as part of Task 1.3. To ensure that all project data share a unified geographic framework, a basic coordinate system (S42) was defined at the start of the project. All project data have been and will be converted to this system.

Fig. 2.1-3: Example of graphic representation of well design (abandoned well UH12)

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geographic framework, a basic coordinate system (S42) was defined at the start of the project. All project data have been and will be converted to this system.

Task 1.1 has been carried out by CGS in cooperation with MND.

Task 1.2 – Overview of available cores and their documentation, sampling selection

This Task represents activity oriented at well cores availability in MND core repository (see Fig 2.1-4). The goal is to access suitable core and cuttings materials for further analyses and take core samples needed for various laboratory experiments and tests (WP4, WP5).

The first phase of core inspection (February - May 2021) suggested that the core repository includes sufficient reservoir rock cores, while caprock cores are available only from the well ZA3 and the old wells UH6 - UH16. During the first phase, 62 core boxes containing cores from wells located in the Zar-3 site and its vicinity have been selected. Core samples of selected cores have been taken for follow-up laboratory experiments in frame of WP4 (geomechanics) and WP5 (geochemistry). For geomechanic experiments, only 17 core boxes were identified as suitable. The selected core boxes and taken core samples are registered in a special “master table” to keep the overviews and see the progress of utilization of samples and results of laboratory experiments.

Search for additional samples of caprock from both Zar-3 and adjacent fields (e.g. Uhřice field) was interrupted in June 2021 due to the damage of the core repository building by tornado; this work will be restarted in January 2022.

Fig. 2.1-4: Selection of suitable cores in MND core repository

Archival data on oil, gas and water properties were collected as complementary input in WP5 (Geochemistry), in addition to the new samples taken from fluids produced by the deep wells that will be subject of laboratory analyses in WP5. Production history data

(2001 - 2021, covered by the Non-disclosure Agreement) for oil and gas per production well have been collected and prepared for use in history matching in WP3 (dynamic modelling) and WP8 (future site development).

Task 1.2 has been carried out by MND in cooperation with CGS.

Task 1.3 – Creation of a project geodatabase (database + GIS)

In Task 1.3, the CGS project team has designed and prepared a geodatabase to host data gathered in Task 1.1 and well core data gathered in Task 1.2, as well as for all other data gathered and created during realization of other WPs. All data designated for upload are verified, analysed and stored in the GIS-linked, structured geodatabase for future use (result R1.3, April 2024). The geodatabase is being maintained and kept updated by incoming, newly acquired data for the whole course of the project and serving as the main project data source for all Work Packages. The geodatabase is available online for all Project Partners, respecting, at the same time, the access rights, limited in some cases by the provisions of the Non-disclosure Agreement between MND and research partners of the project.

The online environment that was set up for the distribution of the data within the project makes it possible to share spatial data with all Project Partners in a safe and user-friendly manner. A repository of the NextCloud environment structured according to access rights to specific data and further thematically, is used for all spatial and non-spatial data saved in file system. For selected spatial GIS data, an ArcGIS Online solution is available for presenting and sharing data with all Project Partners.

Currently stored map compositions available via ArcGIS Online:

- Area of interest
- CO₂ emission sources in the area of interest
- Geology 1:50,000 (Seamless geological map of the Czech Republic 1:50,000)
- Hydrology & Hydrogeology
- Landscape & Natural protection layers
- Mineral resources (Mineral deposits and resources, Mining or production leases, Protected areas of mineral deposits, Exploration licence areas, Protected territories for special intervention into the Earth's crust)
- Soils 1:50,000 (Soil map of the Czech Republic, 1:50,000)
- Topography 1:50,000 (Topographic layers 1:50,000, incl. linear infrastructure layers and administrative division)
- 3D well trajectories
- Wells

All Project Partners can view the data in the prepared map compositions. They can combine individual layers and create their own map compositions (change symbols, create labels, change transparency, etc.) that they can download for further use or can save as an image. Each data layer can be exported to a wide range of formats (shp, KML, FGDB, GeoJSON) and can be used locally.

Within an additional activity of Task 1.3, a digital elevation model (DEM) for the site area has been developed to be used as the basic input for WP2 for creation of the static geological model of the storage complex and utilisation in other WPs (WP6, WP8). The DEM is based on available altimetric data (planimetric coordinates with elevation data, LIDAR data) and incorporated into the project geodatabase.

On Programme Operator request, a Data Management Plan (DMP) was created as an additional output of the CO₂-SPICER project. The DMP describes the data and data handling procedures and workflows in the project (Fig. 2.1-5). The main objective of the project - preparation of a CO₂ storage pilot to an implementation-ready stage - is strongly reflected in the DMP. In particular, this is demonstrated by the fact that the main project results (e.g. 3-dimensional models, results of numerical simulations, site development scenarios), including the corresponding datasets are being prepared for immediate re-use by the industrial Project Partner for the implementation of the pilot storage project as such.

Fig. 2.1-5: Schematic workflow diagram depicting the data sources and procedures of data handling within the project

The Data Management Plan is guided by the key project documents where the key principles of data collection, generation, consolidation and storage are described, as well as the basic rules for access to the most important datasets and their re-use. These documents include:

- Project application – defines Main project results, including the related datasets and the access to these results.
- Partnership Agreement – defines the ownership of and access rights to project results, which also covers the included datasets, and, in its Attachment 1, the Background that the partners make available to the project consortium, including

data. Specific limitations and conditions for implementation and exploitation of the Background are specified here.

- Non-Disclosure Agreement signed between the industrial partner and project site operator MND and the research partners that defines the rules for provision and utilisation of MND proprietary site-specific data in CO2-SPICER.

The Data Management Plan is enclosed with the project Interim report as its attachment in the ISTA system.

Work in Task 1.3 has been carried out by CGS.

Deviations and changes

The only minor deviation from the plan is the interruption of core inspection and sampling activities in Task 1.2 due to the damage of the MND core repository at Lužice caused by the tornado in June 2021. The incurred delay will be made up in 2022.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.2 WORK PACKAGE 2 – 3D geological model of the storage complex

Summary

The main goal of this Work Package is to build a static 3D geological model of the storage complex with particular focus on storage reservoir and seal properties, using seismic and other geophysical data, geological interpretations and well data acquired within WP1. The work started in November 2020 and was performed by MND (WP leader) and CGS, with contributions by NORCE.

As a first step, the model was built in time domain showing the structural phenomena. Then the model was converted to depth domain using seismic velocities model. Two versions of 3D static geological model of Zar-3 were prepared by MND and CGS; MND focused on detailed modelling of the reservoir and the adjacent aquifer while CGS concentrated on broader model of the whole storage complex. The latest version of the reservoir model is shown in Fig. 2.2-1. In the next phase, a final version of the reservoir model will be built as an input for the dynamic model to be used in WP3. The simplified broader model of the whole storage complex, including the reservoir overburden will be finalised to analyse the seal efficiency and risk of fluid migration into shallower aquifers in WP6.

Fig. 2.2-1: 3D static reservoir model of the Zar-3 field and its surroundings (version 12/2021).

Task 2.1 – Interpretation and modelling of the reservoir zone, overlying and underlying rocks and faults

For the interpretation of seismic and well data, the latest version of Petrel software by Schlumberger was used. In the first phase, all necessary data were gathered from WP1 and imported to the interpretation software. Detailed analysis of well logs and well cores was done and stratigraphic profiles were set for individual wells based on the final well reports. Derived interval velocities were used for calibration of check shots (sonic, density and derived acoustic impedance and reflection coefficients). Synthetic seismograms were

generated for detailed seismic to well tie, which was necessary for a correct 3D seismic data interpretation, and for frequency analysis for the calibration of 3D seismic data to well results. Detailed geological interpretation of the most recently processed 3D seismic data was performed both in Xline and Inline directions covering the Zar-3 oil and gas field and its vicinity as a future CO₂ storage site. An example of stratigraphy and faults interpretation in a seismic section (Inline 2415) is shown in Fig. 2.2-2.

Fig. 2.2-2: Interpreted seismic section through the Zar-3 storage complex along the Inline 2415.

Task 2.2 – Lithofacies analysis

Depositional environments of the reservoir dolomites were characterized using detailed analyses of core samples, well logs and mud logs (Fig. 2.2-3 and 2.2-4). Two key facies types were identified within the reservoir. Dolomitic sandstone of the Nikolčice Fm. was deposited by the end of the Middle Jurassic and the dolomites of the Vranovice Fm. were formed in the Upper Jurassic. The original limestones were dolomitized during the early diagenesis. Marls of the Mikulov Fm. form the first seal of the system.

All available exploration data were used to provide lithological interpretation of the Nesvačilka Paleovalley sedimentary fill. Siltstones dominate the Žarošice Member of the Middle Paleogene, which overlie the carbonate reservoir on the E and SE. Ongoing geochemical and microscopic petrographic analyses of the core samples will provide more lithofacies details for the final reservoir model (see also WP5 – Geochemistry).

Fig. 2.2-3: Jurassic lithofacies and lithostratigraphy of the SE margin of the Bohemian Massif (modified from Ladwein 1988, Eliáš and Wessely 1990 and Adámek 2005).

Fig. 2.2-4 Example of a set of well logs, mud logs and derived velocity logs used for lithofacies analysis.

Task 2.3 – Construction of the static model

Inputs from Task 2.1 and 2.2 were used for construction of first versions of the static reservoir model. In the first step, the model elements were defined in time domain, then all key surfaces were converted from time to depth. The cell size used for Zar-3 reservoir model was set at 50 m in both directions. Tops and bases of key seismic/stratigraphic boundaries were interpreted using seismic data calibrated by the wells in the time domain (Fig 2.2-4). They include the thrust plane of the Carpathian Flysch nappes, tops of the Pre-Tertiary, Mikulov Fm., Vranovice and Nikocice Fms., Lower Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm., Devonian Carbonates, Devonian Basal Clastics, and top of the crystalline basement (Fig. 2.2-5, 2.2-6 and 2.2-7).

Fig. 2.2-5: Seismic sections along Xline 2633 and Inline 2415 with interpreted thrustplane of the Flysch units, Paleogene (Pg), Jurassic (J) seal (Mikulov Fm.) and reservoir (Vranovice Fm.), Lower Carboniferous (C1), Devonian carbonates (D) and crystalline basement (Cr).

Fig. 2.2-6: Depth contour maps of the base (left) and top (right) of the Upper Jurassic Vranovice Fm. with underlying Devonian carbonates and Carboniferous siliciclastics (left) and overlying Mikulov Fm. and Paleogene Žarošice Mb. (right) shown by different colours.

Fig. 2.2-7: Thickness contour map of Upper Jurassic Vranovice Fm. at the Zar-3 structure and a 3D view of the model in depth domain.

Fault systems were interpreted to define tectonic boundaries of the key horizons. All key faults were also converted from time to depth domain and some of them were then used as a boundary for pillar grid of the static reservoir model. After pillar gridding, the top, mid and base skeleton was created (Fig. 2.2-8), covering all necessary depth intervals within the model. The Zar-3 model ranges from 800 to 1700 m TVD.

Horizons were made from the tops and bases with 100 m distance set for active faults. The gaps were filled using the convergent gridded and input surfaces were used directly. The resulting horizons were adjusted by available stratigraphic boundaries in the wells. Zones were made afterwards for the defined reservoir model boundaries. Two zones (facies) described in Task 2.2 were modelled in detail. The shape of the Nikolčice Fm. zone was based mainly on the well data, as the seismic data did not provide sufficient resolution to define the zone. For the Vranovice Fm. zone top, the depth-converted interpretation of 3D seismic was used, as well as for the base of the reservoir zones.

The layering within the model was done separately for both facies/zones. For both of them, 10 m cell thickness was used for calculation. For the division of the zones, the “follow base” parameter was used that generally honours the interpreted morphology of the base of each zone. These settings can be changed and edited if necessary, after the fourth model iteration is checked by the reservoir engineers.

Fig. 2.2-8: Skeleton of the 3D model of the Zar-3 field with wells and the tops and bases of key lithological and stratigraphic horizons.

Task 2.4 – Fracture analysis and modelling

The fracture analysis was done using FMS log data (example in Fig. 2.2-9). The Zar-3 field was penetrated by 9 wells, 4 of them are horizontal. Seven of the wells, including the pilot one (ZA3), were logged by FMS (by Schlumberger). Several conclusions were reached during the analysis. Firstly, data from the ZA4A well should be discarded. The tool rotation (even though deemed within limits by Schlumberger) is obviously compromising the results. Secondly, the fractures denoted as bedding planes should be included to the reservoir model as fractures, because no bedding can be recognised in the cores. Thirdly, a broader discussion should be initiated about resistive fractures in wells ZA7 and ZA14H because they were most probably misinterpreted and should enter the fracture modelling as “normal” fractures opened to fluid flow. Contoured equal-area plot of all fractures that should be used in the fracture model is presented in Fig. 2-2-9. Five major systems can be defined with the following azimuths (dip directions) and dips: 127/2, 88/23, 344/35, 254/26, 185/11. Fracture modelling (to be continued in 2022) should of course be based on “real” fractures derived from FMS data in each well as well as their densities.

Fig. WP2.2-9: Example of fracture analysis using FMS log data (a) with contoured equal-area plot (b) demonstrating the azimuths (dip directions) and dips of the fractures.

Task 2.5 – Distribution of petrophysical properties and fluids

A working version of distribution of petrophysical properties within the reservoir model was prepared at the end of 2021 (Fig. 2.2-10). It is based on the well logs and derived calculations (Task 2.2), and calibrated by laboratory core analyses. Two main reservoir properties, porosity and permeability, were simulated in the model. Both properties were first upscaled into the cells penetrated by wells and the values were used for further calculations. The “neighbour cell method” using the “arithmetic average method” was used for upscaling of those active cells. Then the petrophysical properties were distributed by several iterations within both zones (Nikolčice Fm. and Vranovice Fm.) separately. “Gaussian random function simulation” was used for both zones with seed number 12,188 (Fig. 2.2-10) to generate the final porosity and permeability distribution. These parameters were tested in the initial distribution iterations, but they have to be checked and agreed by the dynamic modellers. The final version of the petrophysical properties distribution and fluid contacts will be incorporated into the static model (Task 2.4) after discussion with, and agreement by the reservoir engineers.

Fig. 2.2-10: Porosity distribution within the Zar-3 reservoir model.

Deviations and changes

No major deviations or changes from the plan occurred in this project phase. The only issue was the late and so far limited engagement of Norwegian partner NORCE, which was mainly caused by the impossibility to organise Czech-Norwegian face-to-face meetings due to COVID-19-related restrictions, as well the cancelled visit of NORCE researchers to the MND core repository in late 2021, due to the same reason. Cooperation between the Czech partners and NORCE will be intensified in 2022 to make up the lacking input by NORCE colleagues.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.3 WORK PACKAGE 3 – Dynamic modelling and simulations

Summary

The main objectives of WP3 are: (i) assembling and history matching of full-field reservoir model of the planned storage site, and (ii) simulation of different options of CO₂ injection pilot accounting for most important effects related to CO₂ storage in fractured carbonate reservoir. The work within the WP3 started with slight delay in March 2021. The work was performed by MND (WP leader) and NORCE.

Task 3.1 – Import of upgraded 3D model and upscaling

This Task will start in March 2022, following the transfer of the upscaled geological model from WP2 (Milestone M3.1).

Task 3.2 – Dynamic data analysis to evaluate well-reservoir and fracture network parameters

This Task is focusing on (i) interpretation of available well test and monitoring data (dynamic data) to evaluate well and reservoir parameters for further reservoir simulations; (ii) designing and carrying out of step rate test of an injection well to understand reservoir response to higher rates (in comparison with current operations) and dynamic behaviour of fracture network (presumably providing majority of permeability of this fractured reservoir), and (iii) coupling of the well test design and dynamic data interpretation with geomechanics assessments in in WP4.

Analysis of dynamic data such as production and injection rates and corresponding downhole and wellhead pressures gives a possibility to estimate hydraulic properties of the reservoir (such as permeability-thickness product), well-reservoir connections and boundary effects (such as aquifer support and sealing faults). Moreover, it also indicates, how well productivity and injectivity evolved with time. MND have collected results of pressure and production rate measurements from previous production periods, which were used in this Task for the estimations described above.

NORCE have reviewed the dynamic data for the Zar-3 field provided by MND and have carried out interpretation of selected well tests in Saphir software. Main focus was on injection tests carried out for the well ZA7 (Fig. 2.3-1), the well which was chosen for the step rate tests planned in WP3. Interpretation of the injection tests using the method of pressure transient analysis (Fig. 2.3-2) allowed for estimation of hydraulic properties of the reservoir and well-reservoir connection. Large uncertainty of the interpretation results was related to fragmentary injection rate measurements and depleted reservoir pressure nearby the well. Accounting for interpretation of other well tests done earlier by MND and also by NORCE in this Task, it was found that the well skin for ZA7 appears to be very large, indicating very poor well-reservoir connection, while permeability seems to be lower than average for the field.

Fig. 2.3-1: Results of two sequential injection tests of the well ZA7 performed in 2004.

Fig. 2.3-2: Interpretation of the injection tests of the well ZA7 using log-log plots of the injection and shut-in periods from Fig. 2.3-1.

Further analysis of the ZA7 well history by NORCE and MND has revealed that the current well performance, well-reservoir connection and hydraulic reservoir properties may vary from those evaluated in 2004, due to an upgrade of the well completion with new fibre-tubing and significant reservoir pressure depletion in the area due to production in nearby wells. This analysis has indicated a need for additional pre-test of the well, before the main step-rate test, to evaluate current well performance in the changed environment (new completion and reservoir pressure). Such a pre-test has been designed by NORCE and MND and carried out by MND in November 2021, but the test goals were not achieved due to unexpected failure of the injection pump.

The main step-rate test (SRT) has been designed by NORCE, based on the results and uncertainties from the interpretation results (Fig. 2.3-1 and 2.3-2) following reservoir conditions and well completion in 2004, as well as injection volumes available at MND facilities (Fig. 2.3-3). This preliminary design will be updated based on pre-test results using a mobile pumping unit, which is now planned for Q1 2022. Consequently, the SRT had to be rescheduled to Q1-Q2 2022 as well.

Designing of the injection testing (both pre-test and SRT) is linked to and coordinated with the passive seismic monitoring carried out in WP7. It is expected that injection at relatively high rates may induce seismic events, e.g. related to opening / closure of natural fractures. This will be used to improve geomechanical assessments and description of fracture dynamics in WP4 and WP3.

Fig. 2.3-3: Step-rate test design based on interpretation of the injection tests of the ZA7 well in 2004 (Fig. 2.3-1 and 2.3-2).

Task 3.3 – Upscaling of geochemical, geomechanical and compositional effects

The Task was commenced in September 2021. NORCE have started preparations for assembling of fit-for-purpose reservoir models to be used in this Task. This will be followed by analysis of PVT and SCAL data available at MND for the field and study of compositional effects. The same models will be further used for studying and upscaling of geochemical and geomechanical effects based on results from WP4 and WP5 to be obtained later on in the project.

Task 3.4 – History match of the upgraded reservoir model

This Task will start in March 2022.

Task 3.5 – Design and simulations of pilot CO₂ injection

Task will start in August 2022.

Deviations and changes

The step-rate test in Task 3.2 was planned to be performed in autumn 2021. It had to be delayed to Q1-Q2 2022 due to technical issues incurred by MND during the pre-test performed in November 2021. This delay may cause some small but not dramatic delay of the beginning of the history match process in Task 3.4.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.4 WORK PACKAGE 4 – Geomechanical characteristics

Summary

The objective of WP4 is to characterise geomechanical properties of the reservoir complex and assess the influence that CO₂ has on mechanical geomechanical properties, in order to qualify or disqualify the investigated reservoir for a CO₂ storage pilot. The work started in November 2020 and was performed by NORCE (WP leader) and VSB, with support by MND. The work was carried out according to the work plan.

Task 4.1 – Geomechanical parameter determination of overburden and reservoir samples

This Task's objective is to deliver data for geomechanical assessment of reservoir rocks and the caprock, which will be used to define geomechanical constraints for CO₂ injection in WP3, as defined by Milestone M4.1 (Geomechanical constraints for injection). To achieve the objective, three types of laboratory analyses are performed, i.e. non-destructive mechanical sample testing, destructive mechanical sample testing, and non-destructive thermomechanical sample testing (to be done in Task 4.3).

Non-destructive sample testing is carried out using the ultrasonic apparatus that measures the travel time of elastic waves through a sample, allowing for calculation of dynamic elastic properties of tested rocks (i.e. Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, bulk modulus). Destructive testing is performed using a mechanical press to apply a stress of prescribed geometry onto the sample until its brittle failure, determining the strength of the rock. Brazilian test generates tensile stress and the test yields the tensile strength of the tested material. Unconfined compressive strength test generates compressive stress in axial direction and yields the compressive strength upon the sample's brittle failure. Triaxial test generates stress in axial direction while the sample is being confined by stress in radial direction, yielding shear strength of the tested sample at given confining pressure.

Geomechanical tests mentioned above require certain shape, dimensions, and aspect ratio of a test specimen from a rock sample under investigation. A set of rock samples representing the Zar-3 field with required qualities were hand-picked at the MND core repository at Lužice and delivered by MND to VSB labs. A sufficient number of samples representing the reservoir rock, i.e. the Vranovice Fm. carbonates, could be selected for geomechanical tests. However, until now, only a single caprock sample of Mikulov marls that meets the required size of 15 cm length and 8.9 cm diameter has been identified in the MND core repository (to be split up and used for Brazilian and UCS tests). Until now, the team lacks sufficiently large intact Paleogene caprock samples that can be used for geomechanical analyses. MND continues their search for smaller samples for stiffness and Brazilian tests; this activity has been, however, interrupted by the tornado on 24 June 2021 that severely damaged the core repository.

Workflow

An experimental workflow has been set up that allows to optimize material usage and joint efforts with WP5 (Geochemistry) - see Fig. 2.4-1.

Fig. 2.4-1: Proposed joint WP4 and WP5 workflow.

The workflow consists of the following steps:

1. Picking core intervals that can produce samples for both static moduli and strength determination, and core floods,
2. Preparation of samples at VSB,
3. Sending the rest of the core to partners at CGS for use in WP5,
4. Thermal expansion coefficient determination – sending the sample back to partners at CGS,
5. Analysing chemistry, mineralogy, porosity, carbon content and facies of rocks,
6. Dynamic mechanical response,
7. Static mechanical response,
8. CO₂ exposure,
9. Cutting pieces of CO₂ exposed samples and sending part of them to partners at CGS,
10. Performing steps 5 and 6 on the remnants of CO₂ exposed samples,
11. Analysing chemistry, mineralogy and porosity of CO₂ exposed samples.

Database and tests

Structure of a working geomechanical database has been designed. The database holds experimental data and represents the format in which will the data be delivered for the purpose of result R4.2 and the subsequent integration in the CO₂-SPICER geodatabase. The structure of the working database is shown in Tables 2.4-1 to 2.4-4. The ID of every

individual specimen consists of “well name”_”core number”_”box number”_”core/specimen ID”. It reflects the planned workflow where the core received from the core repository is first measured for its dynamic properties and then individual specimens, identified by lowercase letters (a,b,c,...), are drilled out of the core (see example in Fig. 2.4-2).

Tab. 2.4-1: Specimen identification data

ID	Well name	Core	Box	Box position	Lithology	X	Y	Z	Test
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Tab. 2.4-2: Petrophysical determination

Porosity (1)	Permeability (mD)	Diameter (cm)	length (cm)	Weight (g)	Density (g/cm ³)
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Tab. 2.4-3: Dynamic stiffness data

v_p (km/s)	v_s (km/s)	v_{dyn} (GPa)	E_{dyn} (GPa)
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Tab. 2.4-4: Static stiffness and strength data

v_{stat} (GPa)	E_{stat} (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Unconfined compressive strength (MPa)	Angle of internal friction (°)	Cohesion (MPa)	Biot coefficient (1)	Thermal expansion coefficient (K ⁻¹)
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Tables 2.4-1 and 2.4-4 are used for both the specimens that weren't exposed to CO₂ and those that were, allowing thus to evaluate the CO₂ influence on petrophysical, poromechanical, and thermoelastic properties. Each type of test that the sample is destined for provides only some of the data listed in tables 2.4-2 and 2.4-4 (no specimen will undergo all the listed tests). Tab. 2.4-1 will be filled in completely for every specimen.

Types of mechanical tests being performed in the scope of T4.1, and parameters they provide are:

- ultrasonic measurements: dynamic unconfined Young's modulus (E_{dyn}) and Poisson's ratio v_{dyn}
- Brazilian test (B) – tensile strength,
- unconfined compressive strength test (UCS): static unconfined Young's modulus (E_{stat}) and Poisson's ratio (v_{stat}), unconfined compressive strength (C_0),
- triaxial test (3ax): static confined Young's modulus (E_{stat}) and Poisson's ratio, shear strength.

Material

Core material has been pre-selected from the list and core documentation provided by MND and revised in the core repository. The list of the samples that were selected for geomechanical testing is shown in Tab. 2.4-5.

Tab. 2.4-5: Core samples collected for geomechanical tests in T4.1

Well name	Core	Box	Box position (m)	Well name	Core	Box	Box position (m)
UH11	4	3	0,61	ZA4A	2	5	0,27
UH3	2a	2	-	ZA4A	3	3	0,29
UH3	4	6	0,7	ZA4A	4	2	0,6
ZA1	24	5	0,6	ZA6A	1	1	0,5
ZA3	3	1	0,7	ZA6A	1	2	0,51
ZA3	3	3	0,7	ZA6A	1	4	0,7
ZA4A	1	1	0,44	ZA7	1	2	0,64
ZA4A	1	3	0,44	ZA7	1	5	0,3
ZA4A	1	5	0,31	ZA7	1	6	0,25
ZA4A	1	7	0,2	ZA3	1	3	0,95

Samples listed in Tab. 2.4-5 were cut and drilled into test specimens of required dimensions and geometry for specific tests listed above. Example of such a procedure is given in Fig. 2.4-2. Samples that are not suitable for any mechanical tests because of their insufficient size and shape were cut in such a way that they have two parallel faces at least 20 mm apart to allow for ultrasonic testing, which, in this case, will be the only geomechanical parameter that can be measured.

ID	Core				Dynamic properties before CO ₂ flooding			
	Well name	Core	Box	Box position (m)	V _p (km/s)	V _s (km/s)	V _{dyn} (GPa)	E _{dyn} (GPa)
ZA4A_c1_b3_Core	ZA4A	1	3	0,44	3,39	1,92	0,27	23,52
ZA4A_c1_b5_Core	ZA4A	1	5	0,31	4,26	1,38	0,44	14,24
ZA4A_c2_b5_Core	ZA4A	2	5	0,27	3,10	1,38	0,38	14,22
ZA4A_c3_b3_a	ZA4A	3	3	0,29	2,72	1,19	0,38	9,77
ZA4A_c3_b3_b	ZA4A	3	3	0,29	2,84	1,24	0,38	10,51
ZA4A_c3_b3_Core	ZA4A	3	3	0,29	2,02	1,29	0,16	9,89
ZA4A_c4_b2_a	ZA4A	4	2	0,60	2,43	1,51	0,33	14,72
ZA4A_c4_b2_Core	ZA4A	4	2	0,60	3,16	1,77	0,27	19,13
ZA6A_c1_b1_Core	ZA6A	1	1	0,50	4,05	2,19	0,29	28,96
ZA6A_c1_b2_Core	ZA6A	1	2	0,51	4,47	2,40	0,30	36,96
ZA6A_c1_b4_Core	ZA6A	1	4	0,70	4,45	2,06	0,36	28,91
ZA7_c1_b2_a	ZA7	1	2	0,64	4,53	1,84	0,40	25,57
ZA7_c1_b2_b	ZA7	1	2	0,64	4,65	1,87	0,40	26,21
ZA7_c1_b2_c	ZA7	1	2	0,64	4,02	1,96	0,34	27,25
ZA7_c1_b2_Core	ZA7	1	2	0,64	4,04	1,91	0,36	26,00
ZA7_c1_b5_a	ZA7	1	5	0,30	3,94	1,80	0,37	23,83
ZA7_c1_b5_b	ZA7	1	5	0,30	5,23	2,27	0,38	37,78
ZA7_c1_b5_c	ZA7	1	5	0,30	5,04	2,68	0,30	48,74
ZA7_c1_b5_Core	ZA7	1	5	0,30	4,93	2,50	0,33	44,62
ZA7_c1_b6_a	ZA7	1	6	0,25	5,41	2,38	0,38	39,40
ZA7_c1_b6_b	ZA7	1	6	0,25	4,64	2,14	0,37	33,99
ZA7_c1_b6_Core	ZA7	1	6	0,25	3,80	1,66	0,38	20,00
UH3_c4_b6_Core	UH3	4	6	0,70	3,34	1,42	0,39	14,08
UH11_c4_b3_d	UH11	4	3	0,61	6,67	2,28	0,43	30,05
ZA3_c1_b3_a	ZA3	1	3	0,95	5,68	3,31	0,24	59,84
ZA6A_c1_b4_c	ZA6A	1	4	0,7	4,79	2,45	0,32	33,48
ZA4A_c3_b3_c	ZA4A	3	3	0,29	2,11	0,82	0,41	4,93
ZA4A_c4_b2_b	ZA4A	4	2	0,60	3,14	1,64	0,31	17,70

Ultrasonic measurements are now almost complete (95 % of planned measurements done) and will be finished in February 2022.

Destructive testing

Geomechanical laboratory of the Department of Mining Engineering and Safety at VSB operates a hydraulic press used for unconfined compressive strength test, Brazilian test, and triaxial test. Their objective is to provide strength parameters of the storage complex rocks as well as their static elastic moduli. The failure envelope will be estimated as a result of multiple triaxial tests.

Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test is being performed on specimens listed in Tab. 2.4-7. Test specimens have strain gauges on to monitor radial strain during the deformation. The hydraulic press rig is equipped with the head displacement log to measure the axial strain during deformation. The data is used to calculate static Poisson’s ratio and static Young’s modulus by relating the acting force to the observed deformation.

Tab. 2.4-7: List of samples for UCS evaluation.

ID
_UH11_c4_b3_b
R_ZA3_c3_b1_a
R_ZA4A_c1_b1_b
R_ZA4A_c1_b3_b
R_ZA4A_c1_b5_b
R_ZA4A_c2_b5_b
R_ZA4A_c3_b3_b
R_ZA6A_c1_b4_a
R_ZA7_c1_b6_b

Triaxial test compresses the test specimen axially while applying radial confining pressure. Due to the addition of acting forces the sample is usually failing in shear mode and the shear strength is dependent on the confining stress magnitude. By performing the triaxial test on multiple specimens the shear failure line can be developed. The tensile strength of the specimen will be used to constrain the failure envelope in the tensile region. Test specimens will be equipped with strain gauges to monitor their axial and radial deformation allowing for static elastic moduli calculation.

Triaxial test is being performed on samples listed in Tab. 2.4-8. The experiments will be completed in March 2022.

Tab. 2.4-8: List of samples for triaxial test.

ID
R_ZA4A_c1_b1_a
R_ZA4A_c1_b3_a
R_ZA4A_c1_b5_a
R_ZA4A_c2_b5_a

Brazilian test uses cylindrical samples with radius-to-height ratio of 2:1. The test yields tensile strength of the material upon the brittle failure of the test specimen. Brazilian test is being performed on specimens listed in Tab. 2.4-9. The work is about 50 % complete and will be finished in January 2022.

Tab. 2.4-9: List of samples selected for Brazilian tests and results measured in 2021.

ID	Tensile strength (MPa)	ID	Tensile strength (MPa)
_UH11_c4_b3_c	-	R_ZA4A_c2_b5_d	-
R_ZA3_c3_b1_c	-	R_ZA6A_c1_b4_b	-
R_ZA3_c3_b1_d	-	R_ZA7_c1_b2_a	3,09
R_ZA4A_c1_b1_c	-	R_ZA7_c1_b2_b	4,25
R_ZA4A_c1_b1_d	-	R_ZA7_c1_b2_c	2,58
R_ZA4A_c1_b3_c	-	R_ZA7_c1_b5_a	5,82
R_ZA4A_c1_b3_d	-	R_ZA7_c1_b5_b	4,58
R_ZA4A_c1_b5_c	-	R_ZA7_c1_b5_c	3,89
R_ZA4A_c1_b5_d	-	R_ZA7_c1_b6_a	1,96
R_ZA4A_c2_b5_c	-		

Task 4.2 – Non-destructive determination of mechanical changes for samples exposed to CO₂

Introducing the CO₂ into a rock-brine system results in chemical processes that alter mineral composition of the rock and chemistry of the brine. Alteration of mineral phase brings also changes in textural, structural, and petrophysical properties of the rock. This process results in modification of the mechanical and poroelastic properties of the rock, altering the stability region in the principal stress space (as in Fig. 2.4-3). Several specimens have been prepared for CO₂ exposure in a joint effort with WP5 (Geochemistry). They are listed in Tab. 2.4-10 along with the type of WP4 experimental tests that will be performed on them.

Tab. 2.4-10: List of samples to be exposed to CO₂ with overview of planned tests.

ID	WP4 test	ID	WP4 test
UH11_c4_b3_a	ultrasonic, UCS	ZA6A_c1_b2_a	ultrasonic, UCS
ZA3_c3_b1_b	ultrasonic, UCS	UH11_c4_b3_d	ultrasonic
ZA4A_c1_b5_a	ultrasonic, 3axial	ZA3_c1_b3_a	ultrasonic
ZA4A_c2_b5_a	ultrasonic, 3axial	ZA6A_c1_b4_c	ultrasonic
ZA4A_c3_b3_a	ultrasonic, UCS	ZA4A_c3_b3_c	ultrasonic
ZA4A_c4_b2_a	ultrasonic, UCS	ZA4A_c4_b2_b	ultrasonic

Triaxial test will provide an estimate of the altered failure envelope of the reservoir rocks. The work on specimens ZA4A_c1_b5_a and ZA4A_c2_b5_a is planned to be done in July 2022, so that the results can be included in project result R4.3. The five specimens at the bottom of Tab. 2.4-10 are already being exposed to CO₂ in a reaction chamber and first data on possible CO₂ induced changes in properties is expected in April 2022.

Task 4.3 – Field stress and strength determination at in-situ conditions, and the effect of cooling

Main objective of the Task is to identify the safe CO₂ injection pressures during repressurization and cooling. Increased pore pressure reduces the effective stresses, and cooling by the injection of cold CO₂ leads to thermal contraction that causes side stress reduction since the lateral size of the reservoir remains constant at depth. Further, any geomechanical weakness due to CO₂ induced rock-fluid chemical interactions identified in Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 will be included here. The combined effect of effective stress changes in the cooled and re-pressured state, and mechanical strength alterations is included in Mohr Coulomb plots.

Field stresses

Literature study on how earth stresses change with depth performed in cooperation with CGS has so far not revealed any site-relevant stress data. Neither magnitude nor stress direction from neighbouring formations in the Vienna basin have been identified. Further, a field step-rate injection test in WP3, that could be used to interpret least side stress, has been delayed. Thus, at this level, the stresses at depth have only been estimated via analytical models based on lithostatic weight and Poisson's ratio-given uni-axial strain conditions. At this stage, nine stress scenarios have been developed (given the current day fluid pressure condition) as starting points before cooling and re-pressurization occurs. To constrain these nine scenarios further, laboratory data on Poisson's ratio will be included as soon as the work in T4.1 and 4.2 is completed. Further, assuming uniaxial strain, the side stress reduction due to cooling via thermal expansion coefficient and stiffness Young's modulus may be estimated. Reduced side stress, with the vertical stress being constant, leads to increased Mohr circle. This effect is included in the red circle in Fig. 2.4-3.

It needs to be said that the precision of the estimate depends on the quality of the input data. Access to realistic field stress data, and more experimental rock mechanical results (ongoing work at VSB) will lift the usability of the prediction.

During the literature study MND provided well drilling logs of rate of penetration. The rate at which the drill bit penetrates the reservoir depends on the weight on the bit and rotation speed (that is also reported), and the mechanical strength of the rock. Analysis of this data has been initiated, enabling interpolation of rock strength between the samples that are tested in the lab. It is on-going work to best combine weight on bit, rotation speed and rate of penetration to identify any contrasts in rock mechanical properties.

Fig. 2.4-3: Example of Mohr-Coulomb plot with Mohr circles of maximum and minimum effective stress at Zar-3. Maximal effective stress is estimated from weight of overburden and current day pore pressure. The least horizontal stress is estimated from Poisson's ratio. The black circle is the current day condition with pore pressure of 120 bar, while the red circle represent the re-pressurized phase (180 bar) and the reservoir is cooled by 15°C temperature drop.

Task 4.4 – Uncertain input data leading to probabilistic faulting and fracturing estimate – maximal CO₂ injection pressure determination

Field stresses, mechanical impact of CO₂ to rock strength, mechanical stiffness and strength and thermal contraction, and plane dip and strike (compared to S3 – the least principal stress) are subject to significant variability and uncertainty. Given the variability in parameters determined from the laboratory experiments, the aim in this Task is to predict the likelihood of failure. The focus is on determining stability of the ‘worst case’ directions of a) tensile opening (plane perpendicular to S3) and b) shear failure (plane oriented at 30-degree dip directed towards S3). The point is to respect and use the variability in rock properties and field stresses etc. to constrain the field operation by quantifying the probability of failure during.

The formulated stability criterions enable this to be tested from case to case, however, to provide a meaningful statistical analysis, a Monte Carlo analysis tool has been developed in Python. This Python script is executed directly from Excel via Visual Basic code that uses input data from laboratory and is formulated via probability density functions (PDFs). Currently, the interplay between Excel and Python has been made, although

fitting the laboratory data with PDFs has not been performed. So far only a synthetic case has been implemented with normal distributions (parametrized by average and standard deviation). This will be extended to include variability in parameters determining stress, stiffnesses and strength. As such, the system works, but it is not yet ready to execute the analysis. The work will continue in 2022-23.

Deviations and changes

There were no major deviations or changes made in the extent or time schedule of WP4.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.5 WORK PACKAGE 5 – Geochemistry of rocks and fluids

Summary

The main objective of Work Package 5 is to gain knowledge about composition and properties of formation fluids, i.e. oil, gas and water, injection fluids, reservoir rocks, and caprock. The work started in January 2021 as planned, and is performed by CGS (WP leader), VSB, MND and NORCE.

Task 5.1 – Geochemistry of fluids

Oil, water and gas samples were collected at Zar-3 in June and November 2021. Archival oil analysis data of the Zar-3 fluids were provided by MND (Tab. 2.5-1). The complete analytical data are stored in the project geodatabase.

Tab. 2.5-1: Results of chemical analyses (performed by MND) of the produced oils from wells at the Zar-3 field.

No.	ZA-well #	Depth 1 m	Depth 2 m	Density at 15°C kg/m ³	API °	Dynamic viscosity at 20°C mPa.s	Paraffins % mass	Sulphur % mass
1	3	1740,5	1780	909,6	23,98	19,40	0,5	-
2	3	1740,5	1780	906,7	24,48	39,90	0,4	-
3	4A	1802,3	1842	910,7	23,80	57,10	0,6	0,160
4	5H	2550,2	2860	910,6	23,75	40,5	0,7	0,154
5	5H	2550,2	2860	916,1	22,87	51,8	0,8	0,147
6	6A	1898,9	2000	911,8	23,55	44,7	1,1	0,155
7	6A	1896,9	2000	909,7	23,95	34,3	0,6	0,128
8	8AH	2338,0	2440	915,3	23,00	39,4	0,7	0,159
9	8AH	2338,0	2440	914,8	23,09	39,6	0,8	0,146
10	8AH	2338,0	2440	900,5	25,54	32,7	0,9	0,154
11	9AH	2201,6	2475	911,6	23,58	46,15	0,4	0,145
12	14H	2116,5	2255	913,6	23,29	46,7	0,7	0,153

New analyses included the gas chromatography of whole-oil samples by flame-ionization detector (GC-FID, Fig. 2.5-1) and gas chromatography of the saturated and aromatic fractions by mass selective detector (GC-MS). In total, 11 oil samples were provided by MND and additional 11 samples originated from the CGS archive, which cover the Zar-3 and neighbouring area of the SE margin of the Bohemian Massif. More detailed analysis of biomarkers and isotopic composition is planned for 2022.

The analytical data for the ZA4A oil suggest that the oil is a mixture of medium grade biodegraded black oil with a secondary, only slightly biodegraded light hydrocarbons. The earlier analysis of basin evolution suggests that the black oil migrated from the source rock and accumulated in Jurassic reservoir during the Middle Miocene and underwent biodegradation (Francu et al. 1996). During a second phase of oil migration in the Late Miocene, the biodegraded oil was diluted by gasoline-range hydrocarbon fraction (Fig. 2.5-1), which experienced since then only a very mild biodegradation.

Fig. 2.5-1: Whole-oil chromatogram of the oil produced from the ZA4A well. Note the presence of relatively well-preserved gasoline fraction (left) in a mixture with medium biodegraded black oil (right), which has almost no n-alkanes and a huge unresolved compound mixture (UCM) indicative of biodegradation.

Formation water samples data are shown in Table 2.5-2. Complete analytical results are stored in the project geodatabase. The data serve as a basis for the CO₂–rock–water interaction experiments (Task 5.4) and modelling (Task 5.5), as well as for the reservoir modelling (WP3).

Tab. 2.5-2: Results of chemical analyses of formation waters from the Zar-3 field.

No	Za-Well #	Depth 1 m	Depth 2 m	Density at 15°C g/cm3	pH	Electric conductivity at 25°C mS/cm	Chlorides Cl mg/l	Bicarbonates HCO3 mg/l
1	4A	1802,3	2842	-	7,09	36,0	12000	2800
2	5H	2550,2	2860	1,0177	7,25	36,0	12700	2480
3	8AH	2338,0	2440	1,0178	8,43	37,5	12200	2150
4	8AH	2338,0	2440	-	7,25	38,3	11700	1880

Gas samples have been analysed by gas chromatography with thermal conductivity and flame ionization detectors (GC-TCD-FID). The chemical composition is shown in Tab. 2.5-3, full data are stored in the geodatabase. Gas samples represent oil-associated gas types with very high amount of ethane, propanes and butanes. Closer characteristics based on isotopes will be provided in early 2022.

Tab. 2.5-3: Chemical composition of gas in the Zar-3 field.

No.	Za-well #	Depth 1 (m)	Depth 2 (m)	Methane (% mol)	Ethane (% mol)	Propane (% mol)	2-MP (% mol)	n-Butane % mol.
1	3	1740	1780	83,31	7,60	0,93	0,33	0,30
2	3	1740	1780	83,372	7,59	0,88	0,33	0,30
3	4A	1802	1842	84,291	7,059	0,60	0,21	0,18
4	4A	1802	1842	84,458	6,988	0,94	0,29	0,23
5	4A	1802	1842	90,615	3,566	0,282	0,088	0,054
6	5H	2550	2860	84,094	5,950	0,595	0,145	0,108
7	6a	1899	2000	82,013	6,617	0,45	0,16	0,15
8	8AH	2338	2440	91,573	4,072	0,445	0,130	0,102
9	8AH	2338	2440	92,070	3,861	0,482	0,145	0,129
10	9AH	2202	2475	86,349	5,254	0,266	0,081	0,044
11	14H	2117	2255	89,087	3,568	0,192	0,077	0,053

Task 5.2 – Microbial activity in the reservoir

A water sample taken from the production ZA4A well, depth ca. 1800 m TVDSS, is undergoing DNA analysis and results are expected to be available in March 2022. More sampling is necessary to evaluate the microbial activity in the broader Zar-3 field area. The preliminary data suggest activity of sulphur reducing bacteria at the oil/water contact.

A review of sampling and laboratory techniques for microbiological investigations was compiled from the publications in order to preserve the true unaltered microbial consortia during future sampling and processing activities. It is clear, that the water comes to the surface as a suspension with oil and gas and that the technological conditions of water production differ both from well to well and from time to time.

Task 5.3 – Geochemistry and mineralogy of rocks

43 core samples were analysed for chemical composition using elemental analysis of organic and inorganic carbon (TOC, TIC and calculated calcite or dolomite, Fig. 2.5-2), x-ray fluorescence (XRF) and mineral composition by x-ray diffraction (XRD, Fig. 2.5-3). The results were uploaded to project geodatabase.

Fig. 2.5-2: Calcite or dolomite content versus total sulphur (TS) in 43 core samples plot as separate lithological groups. For legend details see Fig. 2.5-3.

Fig. 2.5-3: Ternary plot of dolomite (Dol), calcite (Cal), and chlorite + quartz + feldspar (Cl+Q+Fsp) of rock samples from various layers of the Zar-3 storage complex: Paleogene (Pg) of the Žarošice Mb., Upper Jurassic (J3) of the Mikulov, Vranovice, and Nikolčice Fms., Lower Carboniferous (C1) of the Myslejovice Fm. The numbers in legend indicate 1 – lower, 3 – upper chronostratigraphic unit.

The Vranovice Fm. represents an end member lithology of almost pure dolomite and iron-rich dolomite, while the underlying Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. is composed of almost pure siliciclastic rocks (shale – silt – sandstone). Mikulov Fm. shows very variable mineral composition, little or minor dolomite, abundant calcite, siliciclastics, and pyrite. Paleogene siltstones are rich in pyrite and have variable carbonate content. The results will be used, among others, for optimization of the experimental conditions of the fluid – rock interactions (Task 5.4).

Fig. 2.5-4: Photomicrographs of the Vranovice Fm. (ZA5H, 2094 m) oolitic limestone (a-b) and Vranovice Fm. (ZA7, 1942.4 m) nonequigranular dolostone (c-d).

Microscopic investigations of thin sections at CGS showed differences in lithology, depositional environment and diagenesis. Photomicrographs of the Vranovice Fm. (well ZA5H, 2094 m depth, Fig. 2.5-4a and b) show oolitic limestone, packstone to grainstone deposited in seaward shoral environment with partly recrystallized and leached matrix, vuggy and mouldic porosity. Fissures are filled with younger calcite. Nonequigranular dolostone (well ZA7, 1942.4 m depth, Fig. 2.5-3 c and d) of the Vranovice Fm exhibits two types of grains: euhedral and subhedral planar dolomite crystals. The rock has vuggy type of porosity.

Microscopy of 33 thin sections of reservoir rocks, provided by MND, was performed at CGS and evaluated in a similar way as shown above; the results were uploaded to the geodatabase and made available to all Project Partners for further use. Thin sections and an atlas of 77 pages of photomicrographs with descriptions were sent to NORCE for further evaluation.

Task 5.4 – Experiments on CO₂ – rock – fluid interactions and a predictive model

Experiments were prepared in 2021 and started at VSB lab in the second week of January 2022, parallel experiments started in late October 2021 in the VSB-partner SUT laboratory in Gliwice. Reservoir rock and caprock samples have been used for the reaction chamber experiments. The characteristics of the samples used at VSB are given in Tab. 2.5-4 and those used at SUT are set in Tab. 2.5-5.

Tab. 2.5-4: Samples used for CO₂-fluid-rock experiments in VSB laboratory.

No	Well name #_ core_box_cm1_cm2	Sample Measured depth (m)	Sample TVDSS (m)	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy Formation	Duration of test (months)
1	UH-11_4_3_61_77	1421.61	1167.34	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	6
2	ZA3_1_3_95_97	1462.95	1240.09	Mid. Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	1, 3, 6
3	ZA4A_3_3_29_44	1789.29	1530.91	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	3, 6
4	ZA4A_4_2_60_85	1831.60	1573.21	Middle Jurassic	Nikolčice Fm.	1, 3, 4, 6
5	ZA6A_1_3_80_90	1931.80	1565.25	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	1, 3, 4, 6

Tab. 2.5-5: Samples used for CO₂-fluid-rock experiments in SUT laboratory.

No.	Well name #_ core_box_cm1_cm2	Sample measured depth (m)	Depth SSTVD (m)	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy	Type of rock
1	ZA3_1_3_95_97	1462.95	1240.09	Mid. Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal
2	ZA4_1_5_51_72	1866.51	1573.41	Mid. Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal
3	ZA4A_4_2_60_85	1831.60	1573.21	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
4	ZA6A_1_3_80_90	1931.80	1565.25	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
5	ZA7_1_6_25_50	1945.25	1641.30	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
6	ZA7_1_7_90_100	1946.90	1642.70	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
7	ZA3_6_2_70_75	1884.70	1661.20	Lower Carboniferous	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal

The rock samples (Tab. 2.5-4 and 2.5-5) together with formation water (Tab. 2.5-2) were placed in PTFE-lined small (SUT, Fig. 2.5-5) and large autoclave chambers (VSB, Fig. 2.5-6).

Fig. 2.5-5: Small autoclave with PTFE lining used in SUT lab in Gliwice.

Small autoclaves were filled with the formation water up to 0,8 volume and closed. Further steps included preflushing with CO₂ – 4 times 5 mins each, pressure set to 2 bars, filling with CO₂ gas to ca. 60 % of the desired storage pressure (approx. 190±10 bar). The autoclaves have been placed in a water bath at the reservoir temperature for 3 months. Pressure has been controlled and additional gas pumped in. The results are expected in March – August, 2022.

In the VSB lab, four cells in the reaction chamber are used for the experiments. The samples were split into several parts to enable multiple experiments. Samples no. 2, 4 and 5 were placed in the first cell (Fig. 2.5-6) for 1 month. Samples no. 2, 3, 4 and 5 were placed in the second cell. Experiment in this cell will take 3 months. Samples no. 4 and 5 were placed in a third cell; this experiment will take 4 months. Samples no. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were placed in the fourth cell and will be exposed to CO₂ for 6 months. Samples in cells were flooded with formation water from the ZA4A well. Chemical analyses of the water sample were provided by MND laboratories. p-T conditions of all tests are: 50°C, 15 MPa. An overview of samples with test duration is given in Table 2.5-4. Results are expected in May – September 2022.

Task 5.5 – Evaluation of changes in reservoir properties during and after CO₂ injection

The Task 5.5 aims at modelling of CO₂–rock–water interactions in the reservoir and caprock formations of the Zar-3 pilot geological carbon dioxide storage complex. The input for the modelling includes the formation water chemistry (Task 5.1, Tab. 2.5-2), mineralogical and petrographical composition (Task 5.3), and petrophysical data (Task 4.1). The models often work with library data, but experiments with real rock samples are

of much higher value. That is why experiments with geochemical simulators have been designed and started at VSB and co-working SUT University in Gliwice (Task 5.4).

Fig. 2.5-6: Preparation of samples for CO₂-flooding experiments in big reaction chamber at VSB laboratory.

The evaluation is focused on determining the mineralogical and porosity changes in rock matrix and in reservoir parameters, which would take place as a result of carbon dioxide injection. Formation suitability for carbon dioxide storage is planned to be assessed. The results will show, how much in the analysed CO₂-rock-water systems (in the selected model periods of years), calcite and dolomite minerals would dissolve and how much ankerite, Ca(Fe,Mg,Mn)(CO₃)₂, and dawsonite, NaAlCO₃(OH)₂, would be able to trap carbon dioxide. Mineral-trapping capacity of carbon dioxide will be calculated for the selected lithological types of rocks in kg per one cubic meter of the formation or related units.

Conceptual modelling is in progress (Fig. 2.5-7) and deals with the main reactions, where CO₂ injection and acidification lead to:

- dissolution of primary carbonates (calcite, dolomite),
- complete dissolution of feldspars in sandstones,
- precipitation of CO₂-trapping phases: newly formed ankerite and dawsonite.

Reservoir conditions are set to mimic the maximum reservoir conditions: static pressure of 17.6 MPa and temperature of 54 °C. The first results are expected in June - Sept 2022.

Fig. 2.5-7: Generalized model predictions of mineral dissolution and precipitation in reservoir- and cap-rocks for the next 1 to 10 000 years. The final model may differ based on the analytical and experimental results.

Deviations and changes

Most of the planned activities have been performed, a minor delay in Task 5.1 is due to delayed fluid sampling, especially limited access to higher number of formation water samples from the Zar-3 field. CO₂-rock-water reaction experiments will probably take more time than planned. Microbiology still needs more fluid samples from different wells in the Zar-3 and adjacent fields.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.6 WORK PACKAGE 6 – Risk analysis

Summary

The main objective of the Work Package is to assess leakage risks related to CO₂ storage in the Zar-3 hydrocarbon field and to compile the findings in a risk assessment report. WP6 was started as the project commenced, beginning sequentially with Task 6.1 – Hazard characterization. Progress has by and large been as planned. The work was performed by NORCE (WP leader), CGS and MND.

Task 6.1 – Hazard characterisation

Task 6.1 was started as the project commenced, beginning with the identification of data needs and requirements for WP6, which was formulated in a dedicated table that was distributed to relevant Project Partners in associated WPs, as shown in Fig. 2.6-1.

CO ₂ -SPICR WP6 Data Requirements - General			
Data	Description	Related to	Priority
Geological formations	Need list of geological formations, where the key informations is the depth of formations, thickness, rock type, shear modulus, poisson's ratio	Wellbore leakage simulations	Medium
Reservoir	Properties of interest are permeability, thickness, pressure, temperature, dimensions, shear modulus, poisson's ratio, oil density, gas gravity, GOR		Medium
Legacy wells - design	For each legacy well, need well design including casing dimension, suspension depth and shoe depth, annular cemented regions, well trajectory		High
Legacy wells - abandonment	Need a document stating requirements at time of abandonment and current requirements. For each well, need plug TOC, plug thickness and perforated zones. If available, any information relating to the quality of the plugs (pressure tests, annulus cement logs, SCP/SCVF). Abandonment (and if relevant, re-abandonment) documentation		High
Caprock	Thickness map	Caprock integrity	Low
Faults	Fault map. Site tectonic assessment (from WP2.1)	Fault reactivity	Low
Maps	Map of area of interest. Location of legacy wells (coordinates). Maps should provide info on any relevant residual areas, important infrastructure, industrial zones, agriculture, water resources (rivers, drinking water, groundwater). Maps should highlight if relevant specially protected areas with respect to vegetation, biosphere, natural habitats, fauna or flora.	Hazard characterization	High
Environmental risk assessments	If previous environmental risk assessments have been conducted, please provide	General	Low

Fig. 2.6-1: Table of data requirements for WP6

The data that has been provided to WP6 thus far includes:

- reservoir map with geographical delimitation and estimated GOC (gas-oil contact) and WOC (water-oil contact) regions;
- stratigraphic maps;
- maps of the area of interest - well locations / residential areas / infrastructure / land use (see Fig. 2.6-2) / hydrology
- list of abandoned wells in the area of interest
- trajectories for abandoned wells
- cement logs for some abandoned wells

Fig. 2.6-2: Land use map of broader area of interest

As part of preparatory actions in WP6, a kick-off and planning meeting was held virtually on June 7th 2021, featuring colleagues from NORCE, CGS and MND. Topics discussed were:

- Consideration of potential leakage pathways, and consideration of potential magnitudes of each (coarse assessment);
- Critical parameters affecting leakage potential, such as maximum reservoir pressure, maximum injection pressure, temperature, assumptions in geological models, etc.;
- Displacement of formation fluids / new substances created by storing CO₂;
- Factors posing threats to human health / environment;
- Area of interest and related stakeholders and risk recipients: Residential areas, industry, infrastructure, land use, flora/fauna, ecological systems, etc.

In the 1st project period, NORCE has had the role of coordinating the Work Package, processing and compiling gathered data, and preparing methodology for leakage simulations from abandoned wells. CGS have provided maps and general information concerning the area of interest, while MND have provided data related to abandoned wells (logs, trajectories, locations, etc.). All partners participated in the hazard identification process and assessment of potential leakage risks as described below.

Based on the initial assessment, three main sources of leakage are considered especially in WP6; caprock integrity, fault reactivation / induction and leakage from abandoned wellbores. The two former ones are reliant on in-depth assessments from WPs 2, 3, 4 and

5, and have thus far been only screened while awaiting results from these WPs. For leakage from abandoned wellbores, the simulation of each well is currently addressed in terms of defining required data for each well, such that well-specific simulations can be run. An ongoing task is also to interpret the cement logs to determine whether information from these could be used to determine quality of the well barriers preventing leakage.

The work part of the initial hazard characterization is currently in the process of being compiled into a summary report, which will also be part of Task 6.4. The plan for 2022 is to complete most of the work of Task 6.1, which will include full leakage simulations of all abandoned wells in the area of interest, assessment of caprock integrity and fault reactivation potential, as well as preliminary (coarse) assessments of consequences in terms of leakage potential.

Task 6.2 – Exposure assessment

This Task will start in February 2022.

Task 6.3 – Effects assessment

This Task will start in February 2022.

Task 6.4 – Risk characterisation

This Task will start in January 2023.

Deviations and changes

The only minor deviation in Task 6.1 was a slight delay of data transfer from WP1, now completed. The start of Tasks 6.2 and 6.3, originally planned for November 2021, has been postponed to January 2022 due to somewhat longer time required to establish and process all required data, and as well the availability of personnel resources towards the end of the 2021. None of these deviations will have any impact on the overall progress of WP6.

A well integrity logging survey was planned in Task 6.1 with uncertain time schedule (2021-2022). This survey is dependent on the plan of well work-overs by MND that are part of the currently running hydrocarbon production operations at Zar-3. The situation in 2021 did not allow for execution of the survey, hence, the suitable survey occasion needs to be found in 2022. As a result, the related sub-contracting costs were not consumed in 2021.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

2.7 WORK PACKAGE 7 – Monitoring

Summary

The main objective of this WP is to prepare a storage site monitoring plan in the sense of Section 9 of the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on the Storage of Carbon Dioxide in Natural Underground Geological Formations. The preparatory work includes an applicability analysis of various monitoring methods, preparation of the baseline monitoring stage including assessment of existing data, as well as execution of baseline monitoring of natural and induced seismicity, baseline atmogeochemical monitoring and baseline monitoring of shallow groundwater, in combination with preparations for reservoir containment monitoring.

The work was started in November 2020 as planned, and was performed by all Project Partners under the leadership of CGS as WP leader. The planned result R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 was successfully achieved.

Task 7.1 – Methods and data

The main aim of Task 7.1 was to analyse internationally available tools and literature to select suitable monitoring methods for the Zar-3 site and assess their fitness for the purpose of site monitoring. Additional selection criteria have been derived from the existing knowledge about the field. The research has involved both surface monitoring methods and those based on well surveys (subsurface monitoring methods), with target depth ranging from the surface down to the storage site horizon level.

The assessment has covered all monitoring purposes and monitoring stages according valid legislation (mainly the Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb.), specifically:

- comparison of the expected and actual behaviour of the carbon dioxide and water present in the storage site;
- identification of significant irregularities in the development of the storage site;
- determination of carbon dioxide flow;
- identification of potential leakages including their volumes;
- identification of potential undesired effects of carbon dioxide on the surrounding environment, in particular drinking water, local population or other local ecosystems;
- evaluation of remedial measure efficiency in case such measures need to be taken; and
- updates to the future compulsory short-term and long-term storage complex safety and integrity reports, including an assessment as to whether the carbon dioxide stored in the facility will be captured entirely and permanently.

The legislation defines parameters to be monitored directly, while monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) are defined indirectly as technologies that "...shall be based on best practice...". The suitability of individual monitoring methods, parameters and detection limits was evaluated using mainly the Guidance Document 2 (EC 2011, an implementation of the EU CCS Directive) and the publication "Best Practices for: Monitoring, Verification, and Accounting for Geologic Storage Projects" (US DOE Best Practices, the National Energy Technology Laboratory of the US Department of Energy, 2017).

According to both the European and US documents, the recommended general principles for the overall approach for monitoring and monitoring plans are:

- Monitoring is risk based, linked to identified risks from site characterisation and the overall risk assessment.
- Monitoring is specific to the storage site and complex.
- Monitoring is linked to preventive and corrective measures.
- Technology used is based on the best practice available at the time of design.

To find the best combination ("applicability matrix") of parameters to be monitored with suitable monitoring methods for Zar-3 site, we have chosen an internationally available, "based on best practice" guideline - the on-line monitoring selection tool named "Interactive Design of Monitoring Programmes for the Geological Storage of CO₂", developed by the Greenhouse Gas Programme of the International Energy Agency (IEAGHG tool). The result of monitoring methods selection, i.e. monitoring matrix for Zar-3 site at the beginning of CO₂ injection, based on this tool, is shown in Fig. 2.7-1.

Tool	Rating %	Plume	Top-Seal	Overburden	Processes	Calibrate	Detect	Quantify	Seismicity	Wellbores
3D surface seismic	64	4.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
Multicomponent surface seismic	56	3.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.0
Downhole pressure/temperature	50	1.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.0
Tracers	44	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	3.0
Geophysical logs	44	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
Deep fluid chemistry	36	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0
2D surface seismic	31	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Integrated tools: behind casing	28	0.7	1.3	0.7	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	2.0
Borehole seismic	28	2.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Microseismic monitoring	24	1.3	2.0	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	2.7	1.3
Atmospheric gas concentration	20	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7	2.0	0.0	2.7
Sonar bubble stream detection	19	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7	1.3	0.0	2.7
Surface-atmospheric gas flux	17	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	2.0

Fig. 2.7-1: Matrix of monitoring tools vs. monitoring aims - results of the IEAGHG tool for the Zar-3 site at the beginning of CO₂ injection

Similar monitoring matrix can be created for the following storage site lifetime steps (injection, post-injection). In general, the IEAGHG tool represents a very useful instrument for basic overview of applicability of various monitoring methods for various monitoring aims at a roughly defined storage site. Its main drawback is that it does not distinguish between various lithologies, especially between clastic reservoirs and carbonates (as Zar-3 site), where mainly the physical and chemical properties of reservoir rocks differ significantly, which also changes the conditions for application of many monitoring methods, in particular those targeting the deep reservoir itself.

That's why we performed a literature review, looking for international practical experience with monitoring of CO₂ storage in carbonates. Two sites that provide the most valuable practical monitoring experience in carbonates were identified - Weyburn-Midale (Saskatchewan, Canada) and the Niagaran pinnacle reefs (Michigan, USA). The review revealed several additional monitoring methods proven at storage sites in carbonates worldwide and potentially suitable for Zar-3 as well. A good example is the pulsed neutron (capture) logging (PNL). PNL method characterizes the vertical distribution of fluids adjacent to wellbore to help monitoring the migration of injected CO₂ through the reservoir during CO₂ injection.

Another source of input information for the study was the overview and quality assessment of existing data collected by the current Zar-3 operator and Project Partners

MND. The 3D seismic data, well logs, reservoir pressure and temperature, Geoservice parameters and well tests were identified as usable sources of the “baseline” status information, with the potential to use repeated measurements for site monitoring.

As a result of the work, a list of monitoring methods suitable for Zar-3 site has been prepared in form of an applicability monitoring matrix (see Tab. 2.7-1), together with recommendations concerning additional work for definition of individual monitoring stages of the Site monitoring plan (to be prepared in Task 7.6).

Tab. 2.7-1: Applicability matrix of monitoring methods for Zar-3 site (number of crosses: 5 = mandatory, 4 = strongly recommended, 3 = definitely applicable, 2 = probably applicable)

Group of parameters to be monitored according legislation	Operational Annex 1.2.	Environmental Annex 1.3. a)	Plume Annex 1.3. b)	Pathway Annex 1.3. c)
Wellhead pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)			
Wellhead flow metering & composition	+++++ (mandatory)			
Downhole pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)		++++	++++
Geophysical logs (well logging)		+++	++++	++++
Tracers		+++	++	+++
Surface seismic (3D, multi-component seismic)		+ to be clarified	+++ to be clarified	+++ to be clarified
Deep (Downhole) fluid chemistry		++	++	++
Borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole)			+++ to be clarified	++ to be clarified
Microseismic monitoring			+++	+++
Atmogeochimistry		++++		
Borehole gravimetry			+++ to be clarified	++ to be clarified

The work was finalized by compilation of the result R7.4 „Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3“ (category „other results“) in March 2021. Result R7.4 is provided as attachment to the Interim report.

The planned feasibility study (sub-contract) to assess the applicability of seismic survey - the most powerful monitoring tool for mapping the extension of the CO₂ plume in the subsurface – at Zar-3 was postponed to 2022 to allow for utilisation of the new 3D geological model of the storage complex that will be completed in WP2 by the end of March 2022.

Task 7.2 – Atmogeochimical monitoring

CGS started the Task in January 2021 with update of the work plan to provide detailed atmogeochimical baseline monitoring of the site area. The main aim was to determine the areal distribution of important soil gas components (CO₂, CH₄, O₂, total petroleum), and identify and monitor anomalies, based on periodically repeated and continuous soil gas monitoring.

For the repeated measurements, a grid of 95 monitoring points was defined (Fig. 2.7-2). At each point, the soil gas composition was periodically measured by the Ecoprobe-5 portable instrument. In 2021, 2 monitoring campaigns were performed – one in spring and one in late summer.

Fig. 2.7-2: Area map with the grid of 95 monitoring points (black dots) used for the periodically repeated soil gas measurements. The red rectangle depicts the detailed area of interest.

For the field data interpretation, the weather conditions, in particular temperature, atmospheric pressure and rainfalls total were collected and stored. During both campaigns, 12 calibration soil gas samples were collected for laboratory chromatographic analysis. Atmogeoechemical maps of the site area showing content of selected components in soil gas (CO₂, CH₄, O₂, total petroleum) and its changes with time are the main outcome of this work. An example is provided in Fig. 2.7-3 where the distribution of soil gas content of CO₂ and total petroleum (methane to pentane) during the 2021 spring campaign is shown. If a large anomaly is found, a separate 3D model will be created.

Fig. 2.7-3: Examples of atmogeochemical maps from the 2021 spring monitoring campaign: distribution of CO₂ (left) and total petroleum (right) content in soil gas.

Fig. 2.7-4: Area map with positions of five IGS stations for continuous monitoring of CO₂ content in soil gas and soil temperature. The red rectangle depicts the detailed area of interest.

The continuous monitoring is performed by five IGS permanent atmogeochemical stations that monitor CO₂ content in soil gas. The stations were installed in the Zar-3 area in June 2021 (Fig. 2.7-4).

First results of the continuous monitoring are shown in Fig. 2.7-5. Significantly higher values of CO₂ content in soil gas can be observed in summer compared to the autumn,

which is caused by the increased vegetation activity. At each IGS station site, a 3 m deep hole was drilled using a soil probe, and a detailed soil profile description was done.

Fig. 2.7-5: Variations of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by five permanent monitoring stations.

Task 7.3 – Seismic monitoring

Seismic monitoring is another representative of basic monitoring methods used for all CO₂ storage sites onshore. In 2021, the work focused on collection and evaluation of historical archive data and first phase of on-site baseline monitoring. This Task is led by GFU with the assistance of MND and CGS.

Historical and recent seismicity reports

Existing seismic bulletins and available archival data for a broader area of the Zar-3 site were compiled to get an overview of historical seismic activity in the region. The results were summarized in the “Report of seismic and macroseismic observation in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Zar-3” and its supplement “Catalogue of tectonic events with macroseismic effect” (authors Z. Jechumtálová and P. Kolář) that was finalised in June 2021. The report consists of three main parts:

- (i) list of earthquakes with macroseismic effect in the region since 1837 (in form of table and map),
- (ii) list of macroseismic observations in closer vicinity of the Zar-3 site (up to 30 km distance; in form of map), and
- (iii) seismic events localized in the vicinity of the site since 1976 (in form of map and catalogue).

Based on collected data we conclude, that estimated value of maximal acceleration in the area did not exceed 0.1g in any case.

Fig. 2.7-6 shows main historical seismic events felt in the region since 1837.

Fig. 2.7-6: Map of epicentres of earthquakes felt in broader area of Zar-3, based on historical archive data.

Seismic monitoring in the field

Five seismic monitoring stations were deployed in the area of interest in Aug/Sep 2021 (Fig. 2.7-7). The characteristic diameter of the net is about 2.5 km and the expected period of observation is about one year. The network design is intended to record local as well as regional activity (if any). Most of the stations (4 of 5) are placed in protected objects of MND, which reduces the probability of damage or loss.

For the seismic station installation, special cases were ordered. Each case includes seismic sensor, digitizer, battery, charging electronic, GPS receiver and recording device. Only solar panels and antennas are situated outside of the case (Fig. 2.7-8). Measured data are stored off-line at the stations; only brief station statuses are sent daily from the stations to GFU. Methods of routine data processing are currently under development, testing and tuning. It is an ongoing task with aim to be able to process recorded data as soon as they will be collected.

Fig. 2.7-7: Area map showing locations of seismic monitoring stations for both long-term and temporal observation, red star depicts the place of planned water injection experiment in WP3; blue and red rectangles mark broader and detailed areas of interest.

Fig. 2.7-8: Seismic monitoring stations for long-term observation – station case with solar panel supplying energy (left); individual parts of the station inside the case (right).

Special temporary seismic observation

To monitor seismicity possibly induced by the experiment (Injection Step-Rate Test: pumping of water into the reservoir through a borehole under step-by-step increasing pressure), another 6 temporal seismic monitoring stations were deployed (in addition to 5 long-term operating stations – see Fig. 2.7-7). The characteristic diameter of this temporal network was about 1.5 km. It was intended to monitor possible seismic activity during and immediately after the experiment. The data were supposed (together with the long-term observation) to enable a more detailed study of expected seismic events, in a favourable case including source mechanism determination.

Due to the technical problems, the injection experiment was carried out in a limited extent only (see WP3 report in Chapter 2.3 for details). It was decided to keep the temporal network in operation anyway. After one month, the temporal stations were collected due to the limited battery capacity. The measured data are currently under processing; an example showing a recorded event from Ostrava region on 28 Nov 2021 (time 08:13:15) is presented in Fig. 2.7-9.

Fig. 2.7-9: Example of a seismic event near Ostrava recorded by the temporal network at Zar-3.

The temporary seismic observation was performed by GFU as an additional activity that was not included in the original project plan. The temporal network stations were provided by GFU free of charge, the only costs laid in travel expenses and software works. Possibilities to deploy the temporal network again in 2022 to monitor the postponed WP3 injection experiment will be investigated by GFU, depending on the availability of monitoring stations.

Task 7.4 – Shallow groundwater monitoring

The shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site, and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development. This Task is executed by CGS and VSB.

The first four campaigns of shallow hydrogeological measurements were performed by CGS in March, June, October and December to cover all seasons of the year. The monitored parameters were groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH (-) and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). A total of 19 points were monitored, e.g. shallow wells, boreholes and springs. Unfortunately, access to some of them was not possible for all campaigns for various reasons, such as new fence construction or the frozen borehole lid in winter. Currently, 16 monitoring objects are still available for monitoring. If necessary, new monitoring objects will be selected for the next campaigns. The position of the monitoring objects is shown in Fig. 2.7-10.

Fig. 2.7-10: Location of 19 groundwater monitoring points on the site.

Groundwater level measurements were performed in several boreholes and wells. Measurements were made with the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy (Fig. 2.7-11).

Fig. 2.7-11: Results of groundwater level measurements [meters] in monitored objects on the site in 2021.

Spring yield was monitored in two cases. The water flowing out of the spring was collected in a container and the time taken to fill the container was measured. From this, the yield in litres per second was determined. The results are shown in Fig. 2.7-12.

Fig. 2.7-12: Spring yields [litres per second] of monitored objects ZA008 and ZA019 measured in 2021.

The conductivity of a groundwater is highly dependent on the concentration of dissolved salts and other chemical species that ionize in the solution. Electrical conductivity of water samples is used as an indicator of how salt-free, ion-free, or impurity-free the sample is; the purer the water, the lower the conductivity and vice versa. Conductivity measurements in water are usually reported as specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 °C. An EC meter capable of providing such values was used to measure water conductivity at Zar-3. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 2.7-13.

The pH indicates the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. At 25 °C, solutions with a pH less than 7 are acidic, and solutions with a pH above 7 are basic. Solutions with a pH of 7 at this temperature are neutral (e.g. pure water). The first measurement results are shown in Fig. 2.7-14.

Fig. 2.7-13: Results of water electrical conductivity [µS/cm] measurements in monitored objects on the site in 2021.

Fig. 2.7-14: Measured water pH in monitored objects on the site in 2021.

The temperature of the water reflects the depth at which it is located; water with a shallow circulation is more reflective of changes in air temperature throughout the year. Water with a deeper circulation shows less variation in temperature values in relation to the seasons. Temperature was measured in degrees Celsius. The measurement results are shown in 2.7-15.

Fig. 2.7-15: Water temperature [degree Celsius] in monitored objects on the site in 2021.

The measured water temperatures reflect the effect of seasonal variations in air temperature and the depth of water circulation. Waters with deeper circulation have less difference between the temperature values measured in the warmer and colder parts of the year than waters with circulation closer to the surface.

The preliminary results of shallow groundwater monitoring show that the data obtained in 2021 correspond to the expected natural conditions characteristic of the site of interest. The monitoring will continue in 2022 as planned, no changes are required. There will be 4 monitoring campaigns in 2022 to cover all seasons of the year.

As part of another activity within Task 7.4, VSB conducted a geophysical survey using dipole electromagnetic profiling (DEMP) on the site. DEMP was performed in three individual field sessions in October and November 2021. A total of 17 profiles with a variable length of 600–1,700 m was measured, covering over 1.2 km² (rectangle ca. 900 × 1,500 m). The DEMP survey was set with 40 m long separation between transmitter and receiver coils. This data will contribute to the construction of the shallow hydrogeological model of the site and will be compared with results of atmogeochemical monitoring in Task 7.2. to better identify or predict possible preferential leakage pathways, and to design effective infrastructure for monitoring of possible CO₂ leakage in the Site monitoring plan.

Task 7.5 – Reservoir containment monitoring

The main purpose of this Task is to prepare a reservoir containment monitoring system. The Task is executed by NORCE and MND, under NORCE leadership.

The advanced monitoring technology developed at NORCE and tested in the EU H2020 ENOS project (Shchipanov et al., 2019¹) is applied in this Task. The technology is based on real-time pressure measurements with Permanent Downhole Gauges (PDG) and employing pressure transient analysis in combination with reservoir simulations carried out in WP3 and WP8.

The well ZA3 (Fig. 2.7-16), which was previously in production, is now used as an observation well. Installing a downhole gauge to monitor pressure in the observation well can be used to get baseline survey of reservoir boundary conditions (sealing faults in combination with aquifer support) and interference with production wells nearby (to evaluate hydraulic properties of the reservoir between the wells).

A downhole gauge, which records pressure and temperature measurements into internal memory, has been installed in the ZA3 well by MND in July 2021 (at the depth of 1760 m MD, which is equivalent to 1755.8 m TVD) to contribute in getting the baseline survey of the boundary conditions and analysing well interference via monitoring pressure response to start of production from the wells ZA14H and ZA6A after workovers.

The first pressure monitoring data set (Fig. 2.7-17) has become available in October 2021 after the memory pressure gauge has been pulled out from the well. Pressure decline from 125.285 bar (27-Jul-2021) to 125.205 bar (06-Oct-2021) with specific behaviour reflecting start of production in nearby wells is observed for the monitored period. The

¹ Shchipanov A.A., Kollbotn L., Berenblyum R. Characterization and monitoring of reservoir flow barriers from pressure transient analysis for CO₂ injection in saline aquifers. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*. Volume 91, December 2019, doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.102842.

data will be used in further analysis and simulations in WP3 and WP7, when full-field reservoir model will be available.

Fig. 2.7-16: Top view of the Zar-3 field with active wells and the observation well ZA3 highlighted with circle.

Fig. 2.7-17: The first pressure monitoring data set for the period of 27-Jul-2021 to 06-Oct-2021 with pressure decline from 125.285 to 125.205 bar.

The memory gauge has been installed back to the well ZA3 after retrieving of the data to monitor pressure in the next observation period, where less changes in production from the nearby active wells are expected, providing better environment for evaluating boundary conditions of the reservoir.

Task 7.6 – Site monitoring plan

Main activity in this Task will start only in September 2023, however, the results from other relevant Work Packages and other WP7 Tasks are being gradually collected, together with experience from other CO₂ storage projects worldwide.

Deviations and changes

Some minor deviations from the work plan were reported in WP7, however, none of them will have negative influence on achievement of WP objectives or execution of other Work Packages.

Task 7.1: The planned feasibility study (sub-contract) on the applicability of seismic survey for monitoring of the CO₂ plume at Zar-3, originally scheduled for 2021, was postponed to 2022. The reason is that it has been deemed useful to wait for the new 3D geological model of the storage complex that is being prepared in WP2 and expected to be ready in March 2022. This model will represent an additional valuable component of input in the feasibility study. The postponement was discussed and approved by the CO₂-SPICER Management Board.

Task 7.2: During the 2021, 2 atmogeochemical monitoring campaigns were performed (spring and summer-autumn ones), instead of 3 planned. The reason for summer field works delay was the requirement of field owners to wait for the harvest campaigns. The winter monitoring campaign has not been performed yet due to the exceptionally warm weather. However, the campaign is planned in January or February 2022.

Task 7.3: The compilation of seismic bulletins and archival data was delayed by ca. 2 months due to COVID-19 measures restricting access to the paper historical archive materials. The spring travel limitations, also related to COVID-19, also caused a slight delay in deployment of long-term seismic monitoring stations. This will be compensated by adequate prolongation of the monitoring period. In addition to the planned activities, an additional temporal monitoring network of 6 seismic stations was deployed to monitor the planned active injection experiment that is part of WP3.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R7.4	Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3	03/2021

2.8 WORK PACKAGE 8 – Scenarios of future development

Summary

The main objective of the Work Package is to prepare future site development plans, and design surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot site. The work has started as planned in 06/2021 and was carried out according to the work plan. NORCE coordinated the work as WP leader; CGS and NORCE provided contributions to Tasks 8.1 and 8.3.

Task 8.1 – Value chain analysis for CO₂ supply, transport, EOR and storage

The first key activity in this Task has been an identification of existing CO₂ emitters in the area that can possibly be interested in storing their CO₂ emissions at Zar-3 or in the region, on pilot, full-field, and regional scales. A database of emitting facilities in a broader area of interest was created with data on location of the facility, its owner, type and amount of yearly emissions. The database contains 16 facilities in distance less than 70 km from Zar-3, with annual emissions ranging from 10 to 700 kt CO₂, and additional 15 larger emission sources with annual emissions exceeding 200 kt CO₂ in broader area of Moravia. A map showing the location of emitting facilities in the area of Zar-3 (distance less than 70 km) is presented in Fig. 2.8-1.

Fig. 2.8-1: Map of CO₂ emission sources in the area of Zar-3. The size of the red circles corresponds to the amount of annual emissions.

The data will serve as input in the full value chain analysis and scenarios focusing on Zar-3 field utilisation for CO₂ storage and broader regional CCS development scenarios that will be prepared in the next stages of the project.

CGS held consultations with two industrial companies that have already declared interest in storing CO₂ emissions on the region – a cement producer and an energy company

preparing plans for low-carbon hydrogen production. Both of them were invited to participate in development of the scenarios and to join the CO₂-SPICER End-User Club.

Task 8.2 – Design of facilities for pilot implementation

This Task will start in June 2022.

Task 8.3 – Scenarios for future site development

One of the key questions for Zar-3 field expansion from pilot-scale to full-field storage is to evaluate the Ultimate Storage Capacity (USC, i.e. the CO₂ amount that the reservoir can accommodate at a given pressure). In this Task the first estimate was done by means of a volumetric approach based on the Material Balance model (MBM, for more details see section 3.5). The MBM sufficiently well reproduced the observed pressure dynamics and that of the simulation model, which suggests that total compressibility is matched reasonably well as shown in Fig. 2.8-2.

Then the MBM was employed to estimate USC for the following preliminary scenarios:

- pure CCS: immediate CO₂ injection without any further hydrocarbon production
- CCS + gas production: CO₂ injection with production of 70 % of the remaining gas cap volume
- CCS + CO₂-EOR: CO₂ injection with additional production of 10 % of the oil originally in place (STOIIP) due to CO₂-EOR (Enhanced Oil Recovery).

The estimation procedure assumed that the reservoir is going to be pressured by CO₂ injection up to a certain pressure while honouring withdrawal volumes, gas dissolution etc. The curves of USC vs. pressure for the estimated scenarios are shown in Fig. 2.8-2. The estimates are indicating USC in the range of 1 million tonnes.

It is worth noting that the presented storage volumes and scenarios are preliminary, based on the available data and will be updated based on the studies ongoing in WP2-WP6.

Deviations and changes

No deviations from or changes to the original plan.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Fig. 2.8-2: Ultimate Storage Capacity (in tonnes) curves for the preliminary scenarios. The lower and upper x-axes show maximum reservoir pressure and pressure relative to the initial one.

2.9 WORK PACKAGE 9 – Communication and dissemination

Summary

The main aim of project communication and dissemination activities is to create awareness of the existence of the project, disseminate project results to identified target groups to achieve the planned impact, raise general awareness of CCS as an important climate change mitigation technology and highlight the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation based on project funding from Norway Grants.

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan. It was governed by the Communication Plan that has been updated from its initial version (contained in project application) in the first month of project implementation (result R9.5). The plan was prepared in cooperation of all Project Partners. It contains a list of planned communication and dissemination activities addressing all project target groups.

CGS led the WP9 activities as WP leader, all Project Partners contributed to the work. All the 7 project results planned for the 1st reporting period have been delivered.

Task 9.1 – Project events

On 5 March 2021, CGS organized the Project Launch event (result R9.3). The conference titled “Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS” was, at the same time, the launch event of two CCS-related projects funded by Norway Grants and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic within the KAPPA programme - CO2-SPICER a METAMORPH.

Due to the regulations taken by the government to overcome the coronavirus epidemic, the conference took place online (Fig. 2.9-1). The guests were welcomed by the ambassador of the Kingdom of Norway in the Czech Republic, H. E. Robert Kvile, the Director of the Czech Geological Survey, Mr. Zdeněk Venera, and the Director of the InoCure company (coordinator of the METAMORPH project), Mr. Matej Buzgo. More than 70 conference participants from 37 institutions from Czechia and Norway were provided with 10 presentations divided into 3 sessions:

- The first session “Setting the scene” offered an idea on the role and status of CO₂ capture and storage technologies in the Czech Republic and Norway and possible ways of their implementation, as well as with insight into broader development context of these technologies in Europe.
- Session 2 – “CCS projects of the KAPPA programme” – was devoted to introduction of the CO₂-SPICER and METAMORPH projects to the participants.
- Session 3 – Other CCUS initiatives in Czechia” gave the floor to other CCS-related projects currently running in the country, including two funded by other mechanisms of EEA/Norway Grants.

All presentations from the conference are available on CO₂-SPICER project website at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads/czech-norwegian-conference>.

Fig. 2.9-1: Screenshot from the Webex SW platform showing part of the participants of the CO₂-SPICER Launch Event

Task 9.2 – Website

A project website “<https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz>” was created in both Czech and English versions, (result R9.8) in the first month of project implementation and made public in January 2021 (Fig. 2.9-2).

It consists of two main parts – public and internal, the latter intended for Project Partners and various internal organisational purposes, such as coordination of activities, project management, data and document sharing, etc.

The public part offers information on the CO₂-SPICER project itself, project news, results and dissemination activities connected with the project, including, for instance, announcements of project events and presentations held at these events.

The website also offers a link to a special information portal dedicated to the CCS technology, operated by CGS since 2006 at <http://www.geology.cz/ccs>. Regular updates of this portal are also part of CO₂-SPICER communication activities.

Fig. 2.9-2: CO2-SPICER website – homepage, English version

Task 9.3 – Presentations and publications

In order to support the presentations and publication efforts of the project, CGS prepared a project graphic style package (result R9.4). The package contains the project logo (including a manual for its use), a PowerPoint presentation template (Fig. 2.9-3), Word document / project report template and background for online meetings and conferences. The created graphic style is also used for the preparation of other outputs like poster template, report cover sheet, leaflet, newsletter, etc. The project graphic style follows the rules set in the Communication and Design Manual of EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021.

Fig. 2.9-3: Project logotypes and PowerPoint presentation template

A project information leaflet (result R9.6) was created in cooperation of all Project Partners in December 2020 (Fig. 2.9-4). The leaflet is available in Czech and English versions, and was distributed in both electronic and printed forms. The leaflet is located on the Czech and English versions of the website at the following links:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni>
- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>

Press release (result R9.7) was created in Czech and English versions (Fig. 2.9-5). Press releases were distributed using the established communication channels of CGS (www.geology.cz, www.geology.cz/ccs) and Project Partners. The press release was further offered to the media and published on the project website at:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni> (Czech version)
- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads> (English version)

Fig. 2.9-5: Press release – English version

In addition, CGS also cooperated with TACR on preparation of a project-related press release issued by TACR in September 2021. Both press releases met with unexpectedly large media response, resulting in further interaction with media (see below).

The first issue of project newsletter (result R9.11) was created in cooperation of CGS with all Project Partners in December 2021 (Fig. 2.9-6). The introductory part of the newsletter contains information about the main activities of the project and its goals. The next section describes the achieved partial results, including project events and reflections in the media. The newsletter was prepared in Czech version only (as planned) and was distributed in electronic and printed forms. It is also available on project website at:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni>

Číslo 1/prosinec 2021

Newsletter projektu CO2-SPICER

Pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ v karbonátovém ložisku

co2-spicer.geology.cz

O projektu CO2-SPICER a jeho cílech

CO2-SPICER je čtyřletý česko-norský výzkumný projekt zaměřený na geologické ukládání oxidu uhličitého. Projevtové konceptem pod vedením České geologické služby zahájily jeho realizaci v listopadu 2020. Hlavním cílem projektu je připravit pilotní úložiště CO₂ na dotábovaném ložisku rosy a plynu nacházejícím se na jihovýchodě Moravy. Zároveň tím vznikne modelový příklad pro potenciální realizaci dalších úložišť CO₂ v Česku i v Evropě. V útiskách úspěšného zavření celkového závěru se bude jednat o vůbec první pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ ve střední a východní Evropě. Realizace projektu CO2-SPICER navíc výrazně zvýší úroveň technologické připravenosti geologického ukládání CO₂ v České republice a zároveň učiní významný krok směrem k reálnému zavedení technologie CCS ve střední Evropě. Říká vedoucí projektu Vít Hladík z České geologické služby. Technologie CCS (Carbon dioxide Capture and Storage – zachytávání a ukládání oxidu uhličitého) se ve světě úspěšně rozvíjí. Společně s zachytáváním CO₂ vypočetného velkými průmyslovými provozny a jeho následným uložením v tekuté formě do hornin hluboko pod zemským povrchem pomohou vrtit. Důvodem je snaha o omezení růstu množství CO₂ – nejvýznamnějšího skleníkového plynu – v atmosféře a zmiňování souvisejících klimatických změn.

Projekt je součástí dlouhodobé koncepce rozvoje geologického ukládání CO₂ v České republice. Jeho úspěšné provedení přinese vzhledem pro další zamyšlená úložiště CO₂ v našich i v evropských podmínkách, ale i reálnou možnost úložně bezpečně využít. Specialisté sestaví trojrozměrný geologický model celého úložného komplexu a budou simulovat injektáž CO₂ do geologického podloží. Důležitý je paralelní výzkum geomechanických a geochemických vlastností úložště, stejně jako analýza možných rizik a návrhem jejich minimalizace a monitorovacím plánem. V projektu CO2-SPICER bude využito množství nových přístupů a metod. Kromě dynamického modelování a počítačové simulace injektáže CO₂ jsou to nejmodernější monitorovací techniky či posouzení možnosti kombinování ukládání CO₂ s bakteriální metanogenezou* dodává V. Hladík. Na projektu se kromě České geologické služby podílí další čtyři partneři ze sféry výzkumu i průmyslu. Tuzemské organizace zastupují MNO a „Vysoká škola báňská – Technická univerzita Ostrava a Geofyzikální ústav AV ČR, v. v. i. Norskou stranu reprezentuje výzkumná instituce NORCE. Projekt CO2-SPICER byl podpořen částkou 2,32 mil. € Norskými fondy a Technologickou agenturou ČR v rámci Programu KAPPA.

T A Č R

Norway granica Programme Kappa

Newsletter CO2-SPICER Pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ v karbonátovém ložisku. Číslo 1/prosinec 2021 co2-spicer.geology.cz

Hlavní aktivity projektu

- 1. PILOTNÍ ÚLOŽIŠTĚ CO₂**
Vznikne trojrozměrný geologický model celého úložného komplexu.
- 2. TROJROZMĚRNÝ GEOLOGICKÝ MODEL**
Bude připraveno pilotní úložště CO₂ na dotábovaném ložisku rosy a plynu nacházejícím se na jihovýchodě Moravy, pro bezpečnější využití. Úložště CO₂ se současně stane modelovým příkladem pro potenciální realizaci dalších úložšť CO₂ v Česku i v Evropě.
- 3. DYNAMICKÉ MODELOVÁNÍ A POČÍTAČOVÁ SIMULACE**
Bude provedeno dynamické modelování a počítačová simulace injektáže CO₂ do úložště.
- 4. ZHODNOCENÍ GEOMECHANICKÝCH A GEOCHEMICKÝCH VLASTNOSTÍ**
Zhodnotí se geomechanické a geochemické vlastnosti úložného komplexu.
- 5. POSOUZENÍ RIZIK**
Dojde k posouzení rizik spojených s ukládáním CO₂ do úložště.
- 6. ZPRACOVÁNÍ MONITOROVACÍHO PLÁNU**
Bude zpracován monitorovací plán úložště a vzhledem jeho dalšího rozvoje.

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Dílčí výsledky projektu

SCÉNÁŘE DALŠÍHO ROZVOJE ÚLOŽIŠTĚ

Tato část projektu je zaměřena na aktivitu, která by měla následovat po úspěšném ukončení projektu a využít jeho výsledky. Jde o vlastní realizaci pilotního úložště a následný rozvoj ukládání CO₂ v celé oblasti. V této souvislosti byly analyzovány potenciální zdroje CO₂ pro pilotní projekt a jeho případné rozšíření a zahájena práce na společném rozvoji technologie CCS v regionu. Byl také zpracován první odhad úložně kapacity zájmové struktury. Práce na scénářích bude pokračovat v dalších fázích projektu a zaměřit se i na design technologických zařízení přímo na úložště.

SLOVO KOORDINÁTORA
Vít Hladík

Projekt CO2-SPICER právě uzavřel úspěšný první rok řešení. Na samém začátku bylo středem pozornosti zhodnocení veškerých dostupných vstupních dat, jejich prověření a seřazení. Na tento krok pak navázaly práce na konstrukci trojrozměrného geologického modelu úložného komplexu, což je střední aktivita této fáze projektu, která bude ještě pokračovat v první polovině příštího roku. Začali jsme rovněž s podrobným studiem geomechanických a geochemických vlastností hornin tvořících úložště a jeho nadobití těsnosti a s ověřováním použitelnosti různých monitorovacích metod pro dlouhodobé sledování uloženého CO₂. Při práci jsme se museli potýkat i s některými neočekávanými obtížemi. Protičividová opatření nám značně zkomplikovala uskutečnění plánovaných projektových aktivit a většinu osobně setkávání v rámci projektu, čímž hodně trpěla zejména česko-norská spolupráce: online setkání buďto osobně konkrétně nenahradí. Náš průmyslový partneř MNO byl navíc v červnu postihen tornádem (viz foto), které ponížilo jeho provozní areál v Lužicích, včetně skladu vnitřních jader a laboratorů. Problémy se nám ale postupně daří překonat a vyhlídky do další etapy řešení projektu jsou optimistické.

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Události a ohlasy v médiích

ČESKO-NORSKÁ KONFERENCE O ZACHYTÁVÁNÍ A UKLÁDÁNÍ CO₂ SE USKUTEČNĚLA ON-LINE

Česká geologická služba uspořádala dne 5. 3. 2021 česko-norskou konferenci Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS a tematickou zachytávání a ukládání CO₂. Konference se s ohledem na vládní nařízení související s bojem proti epidemii koronaviru konala on-line a úvodního přítvlní hostů se ujali velvyslanec Norského ložstovství v ČR Robert Kuliš, ředitel České geologické služby Zdeněk Věna a ředitel společnosti InoCare Matej Buzga. Pro více než 70 účastníků byly připraveny prezentace přibližující technologie zachytávání a ukládání CO₂ v ČR i z pohledu jejich implementace, a zároveň vzhledem do širšího kontextu vývoje těchto technologií v celé Evropě.

Konference byla rovněž zahájena událostí projektu CO2-SPICER a METAMORPH, které jsou zaměřeny na výzkum a vývoj technologií zachytávání a ukládání CO₂ a jsou podpořeny grantem Norska a Technologické agentury České republiky prostřednictvím programu KAPPA. Prezentace, které na konferenci zazněly, jsou ke zhlédnutí na webu projektu CO2-SPICER – <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads/czech-norwegian-conference>.

ČLÁNEK O PROJEKTU CO2-SPICER V MF DNES

DNES

Brno a Jižní Morava

Oxid uhličitý ukryjí do ropného vrtu

Noviny MF DNES pro Brno a Jižní Moravu uveřejnily 29. 4. 2021 článek Evany Šalkůvcové o realizaci česko-norského projektu CO2-SPICER. Článek s názvem „Oxid uhličitý ukryjí do ropného vrtu“ je dostupný prostřednictvím přiloženého QR kódu.

Newsletter CO2-SPICER Pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ v karbonátovém ložisku. Číslo 1/prosinec 2021 co2-spicer.geology.cz

Fig. 2.9-6: Sample of newsletter pages

In 2021, the project and its results were presented at four international conferences; the following talks were given:

- [Comparison of two candidate hydrocarbon fields for a CO₂ storage pilot in the Czech Republic](#). Presentation of results of CO₂-SPICER, REPP-CO₂ and ENOS projects at the 2nd EAGE Geoscience and Engineering for the Energy Transition Conference (GET2021); online (November 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, M. Pereszlényi (CGS), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermon, E.P. Ford (NORCE).
- [CO₂-SPICER: Czech-Norwegian project to prepare a CO₂ storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir](#). Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the 11th Trondheim CCS conference (TCCS-11); online (June 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, P. Jirman (CGS), V. Opletal, M. Pagáč (MND), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, E. Ford, A. Nermon (NORCE).
- [Diagenesis and dolomitization of Jurassic carbonate rocks in the SE Bohemian Massif](#). Presentation of research results related to Jurassic carbonates, including CO₂-SPICER project, WP5, at the 35th IAS Meeting of Sedimentology; online (June 2021). Authors: J. Franců, L. Jurenka, P. Jirman (CGS).
- [Assessment of trans-boundary effects at LBr-1 CO₂ storage pilot site and regulatory solutions](#). Presentation of results of REPP-CO₂, ENOS and CO₂-SPICER projects at the 15th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies conference (GHGT-15); online (March 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, J. Franců, V. Kolejka, M. Pereszlényi (ČGS), L. Kollbotn, E. Ford (NORCE), M. Jankulár (ŠGÚDŠ), M. Koenen (TNO).

In addition to the presentations, the related papers or paper abstracts were published in conference proceedings of these events. All presentations and publications are available on project website at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>.

An important part of communication activities was the liaison with other project funded by EEA/Norway Grants. A joint Launch event was organised together with METAMORPH – the sister CCS project of the KAPPA programme (see above).

Intensive cooperation was established between CO₂-SPICER and the CCUS CZ-NO project (Technological cooperation of companies in the field of capture, storage and use of CO₂) funded from the EEA/Norway Grants' Fund for Bilateral Relations and coordinated by BeePartner a.s. CO₂-SPICER coordinator Vit Hladik provided advice to the project in the area of CO₂ storage, made presentation on CO₂ storage conditions in Czechia at the Conference on CO₂ capture, storage and use for Czech industrial companies organised by CCUS CZ-NO in April 2021 and participated in a study visit of Czech industrial companies to the Technology Centre Mongstad. This opportunity was also used for extensive discussion with the participating Czech industry representatives on CCS in general, as well as on their possible engagement in CO₂-SPICER End-User Group.

A similarly close relationship was created with the CCS4CEE project (Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region, <https://ccs4cee.eu/>), especially with its Czech partner EUROPEUM. This project is funded from the Fund for Regional Cooperation of EEA/Norway Grants. CO₂-SPICER coordinator provided advice to EUROPEUM in support of the work on the report “Assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region”, reviewed the report and actively participated in CCS4CEE events.

Good relationship was established with the Royal Norwegian Embassy in Prague with respect to support of Czech-Norwegian cooperation on CCS and possible Norwegian support of the development of the CCS technology in Czechia. This activity was initiated by Mr. Geir Bekkevold, the Deputy Head of Mission, and included several consultations, active participation in the Norwegian-Czech CCS webinar organised by the Embassy in September 2021 (with presentations of CO₂-SPICER project by R. Berenblyum, NORCE and [History of Czech-Norwegian cooperation on CCS](#) by V. Hladik, CGS) and engagement in several CCS-focused meetings with Czech Ministries and authorities organised by the Embassy.

Communication activities addressing industrial stakeholders included a series of bilateral consultations, both face-to-face and online, that were devoted to possibilities of utilisation of CCS technology as a solution for reduction of CO₂ emissions from industrial facilities, sharing information about the CO₂-SPICER project, discussions on future utilisation of its results and possible participation of the industry representatives in CO₂-SPICER End-User Group (often with encouraging results). The consulted companies included Českomoravský cement, C-Energy Planá n. L., LAMA Gas & Oil, Třinecké železářny, Liberty Steel, SMOLO a. s., MERO, Net4Gas and UNIGEO. Consultations were also provided to the Ministry of Industry and Trade and the State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic.

Another important target group of project communication is university students. The COVID-19-related restrictions did not allow for giving the planned lectures. However, the university Project Partners VSB attracted several students of the university (VSB - Technical University of Ostrava) to use topics solved within CO₂-SPICER as a basis for the final theses:

- Bachelor thesis:
 - Josef Čožík: Utilization of Dipole Electromagnetic Profiling for CO₂ Monitoring Optimization at the Žarošice Site
- Master's thesis:
 - Janani Augustin: Design of a Methodology for Laboratory Research of Filtration Parameters of the Rock - CO₂ System of the Žarošice Oil Field
 - Tereza Svěchová: Description of selected samples from drilling cores based on laboratory analyzes for the needs of CO₂ geosequestration
- PhD dissertation:
 - Adam Lacman: Research into the Influence of Carbon Dioxide on the Reservoir Properties of the Žarošice Oil Field

CO₂-SPICER project implementation attracted relatively high media interest, supported, among other, by the two press releases mentioned above. Information about the project, its objectives, status of solution, but also the overall status and perspectives of the CCS technology both in Czechia and worldwide were the main topics of interest. Written information, as well as interviews with journalists were provided to media. Not only thematically profiled media, but also those with nationwide coverage were interested in the project. In total, information about the project appeared in the media more than 30 times. Examples are shown in Fig. 2.9-7 and 2.9.8.

An overview of project media coverage is available on project website (Czech version) at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/zajimave-odkazy>.

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titulní strana | zpravodajství | publicistika | zelená domácnost | kultura | kalendář akcí | fotobank

zprávy | tiskové zprávy | co přijít jít | speciály

Roste globální zájem o technologie na zachytávání oxidu uhličitého. První projekt se chystá i v Česku

20.10.2021 01:19 | PRAHA (ČTK)
» Diskuse: 8

Technologie CCS společnosti Shell Scotford, Fort Saskatchewan, Alberta
Licence | © @ @ @ Některá práva vyhrazena
Foto | Roberta Franchuk, Pembina Institute / Flickr

Roste globální zájem o technologie na zachytávání a ukládání oxidu uhličitého (CO₂). Podle nejnovější zprávy mezinárodního think-tanku Global CCS Institute se celkový počet komerčních projektů ve fázi přípravy a provozu letos zvýšil o 71 na 135, tedy o 90 procent. Plně v provozu je podle ní 27 zařízení, čtyři jsou ve výstavbě a 102 v různých fázích přípravy. První pilotní projekt se chystá také v Česku.

ROZHOVOR

Bez ukládání CO₂ klimatické neutrality nedosáhneme

I Redakce OF

Pro technologie CCS (carbon capture and storage) zatím neexistuje „business case“, přinejmenším v evropských podmínkách. Náklady na takto odstraněnou jednu tunu CO₂ jsou pořád vyšší než cena emisní povolenky. Ta se ovšem bude do budoucna zvyšovat a jakmile převyší úroveň nákladů, technologie se stane rentabilní a začne se mnohem více prosazovat. O perspektivě CCS jsme hovořili s Vitem Hladíkem z České geologické služby.

ENERGETIKA

VRAŤ SE POD ZEM

V Česku vzniká unikátní projekt na podzemní ukládání emisí z průmyslu

Petr Weiskert
Kjetil Alvik

Za bývalou železnou oponou ještě podobný projekt neexistoval. V Česku se začne reálně zkoumat dožehované ložisko ropu a zemního plynu proto, aby se otáčovalo, jak pod zem dostat oxid uhličitý. Mělo to zít na první poslech banální, ale ve hře je zrod úplně nového byznysu pro těžařské firmy, a hlavně evropské miliardy, které poputují v příštích letech na ochranu klimatu. Právě oxid uhličitý mají zachytávat největší znečišťovatelé a hledá se, kam s ním.

Znovu ve hře
Pro lajnémkry z oboru nejde o nic převratného. O podzemním ukládání oxidu uhličitého se v Česku hovoří již před třiceti lety a podobně jako v jiných zemích se přišlo na to, že je to myšlenka sice zajímavá, ale také hodně drahá. Aby nevyspítila, největší znečišťovatelé, jako

Jedno ze zmi, kde se zachytává a ukládá oxid uhličitý, je Norsko, kde skleníkový plyn putuje pod mořské dno.

Přesné v této době přichází Česká geologická služba s projektem CO₂-SPICER. Podílí se na něm i akademická síla, financovaná poskytl norské fondy

ložiska se totiž dají použít netežně uhlé sloje, což už je pro Česko zajímavější nápad. Vhodné geologické podmínky pro ukládání by mohly být třeba i ve středních a východních Čechách, přičemž tam ale neprobíhá, protože nic „zajímavého“ pro potřeby průmyslu tam pod zemí nikdy nebylo. Ještě pro ukládání dojde, že CO₂ se ukládá v hloubkách

MLADÁ FRONTA DNES | čtvrtek 29. 4. 2021

Brno a jižní Morava

20 °C | 7 °C

Počasí v kraji více informací →
pocasi.dnes.cz

DNES Brno, Blansko, Břeclav, Hodonín, Vyškov, Znojmo

Oxid uhličitý ukryjí do ropného vrtu

Na jižní Moravě vzniká první podzemní úložiště CO₂ ve východní a střední Evropě. „Problémový“ plyn do něj uloží třeba teplárny.

Světový boom Oxid uhličitý, vypouštěný velkými průmyslovými provozy, se ukládá do hromin hluboko pod zem pomocí vrtů. Ilustrace foto: ČTK

Zachycování uhlíku může prodloužit životnost uhelných elektráren. Rozhovor s šéfkou ...
Článek

SZ | Seznam Zprávy

00:26 / 18:22

Uhlík je třeba dostat zpátky pod zem. Evropská Zelená dohoda se bez technologie CCS neobejde, říká Vít Hladík

VITĚCH KRISTEN

Fig. 2.9-7: Samples of articles in the media – part 1

Češi se od Norů učí ukládat CO₂

Rostoucí ceny emisních povolenek přerušují řadě eur za tunu oxidu uhličitého a dříve na ekologičtější evropského průměru nabývají příležitost brzy se zaklárem na relativně staré technologii ukládání zkapalněného plynu pod zemí alias CCS (Carbon Capture and Storage).

„Fungující business case pro tuto technologii zatím neexistuje, vše je stále pod hranicí ekonomické výhodnosti“ věřína již řadě projektů ve světě je dotována nebo nějak státními dotacemi, například v Norsku je poměrně vysoká část z výpočetní oxidu uhličitého. Do budoucna by to mohlo být i u nás, zejména v rámci projektu Vít Hladík z České geologické služby.

Přívěs má na starosti koordinaci ambiciózního tušeného výzkumného projektu CO₂-Spicer, který představuje kompletní přípravu pilotního a do budoucna komerčního využití oxidu uhličitého zkapalněného oxidu uhličitého na dotovaném ložisku ropy a plynu.

Heslo by mělo být na jaře roku 2024. To by tým odborníků z České geologické služby, Vysoké školy báňské, Geodyšálního ústavu Akademie věd, firmy MIRA a z norského výzkumného centra NORCE měl mít vše připraveno. „Pochtěme sledovat všech legislativních postupů pro velké množství tun oxidu uhličitého, což je naše hlavní cíl“ říká Hladík. „Někdo to u nás nikdy neudělá, musíme provést jak geologické průzkumy, tak ty regulační a právní“.

Jihovýchodní Morava je klíčová
Potenciál pro ukládání oxidu uhličitého do hloubky přesahující 800 metrů má hlavně východní část Česka a středovýchodní permafrost,

tedy lokality například v Jatecké, mělnicko-rosoučnické nebo v michovotrančické pánvi. Češi v Norsku zatím předpokládají, že místem pro zbudování prvního úložiště by se měla stát vlnodílná mořská lokalita ZAR-S, kde firma MIRA se spolupráce E.ON a Karla Tomáše má již spuštěný ložiskový test.

Díky tomu, že je k dispozici v provozu, umožňuje přístup nejen k aktuálním geologickým datům, ale také přímo do geologické struktury. Za takovéto potřebné testy ve vrtěch či ovládnutí sondy. „Kdybychom využili jejich znalosti, zkušenosti, odborníky vrtů a infrastruktury a měli se tak důležitou součástí CCS aktivní v Česku“ reagovat Michal Šolín z ústavu vývoje nové technologie MIRA. Firma podle něho plánuje na projekt byznysové nasazení.

„Jméno přivádějí, že CCS projekt přičítá vrtů jedny z klíčových technologií pro uhlíkové řešení. Zdejší geologické podmínky, zejména vrtů, jsou velmi podobné těm, které máme v Česku“.

Známí, ale drahá práce
Ukládání oxidu uhličitého do podzemí není jen teoretická možnost. „V první to funguje už dlouho. Existuje řada geologických systémů, v nichž se oxid uhličitý přirozeně ukládá desítkami tisíci let. Společně tak se již více než čtyřicet let bez problémů využívá ze zvláštní úložiště roty roty z podzemí“ upozorňuje Petr Komárek, předseda Technologické agentury ČR. Ta na projekt o celkových nákladech 60 milionů korun poskytl 60 milionů, z nichž 40 procent pochází z Norských fondů.

Norské centrum NORCE je partnerem pro jedno z tzv. know-how, které česť využívá, a to vrtů v otázkách geomechaniky rezervoáru, posouzení analyzy rizik a dynamického modelování samostatně ingibitce plynu. „Novově přetavují špičku, mají jedny z největších úložišť oxidu uhličitého na světě. A to se bereme uhlíkem saturací až miliony tun zkapalněného plynu ročně“ upozorňuje Hladík.

Cena za vybudování průmyslového úložišť s kapacitou milionů uloženců tun ročně se

Marek Schwarzmann

Česko-norský pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ pod zem pomůže s bojem proti klimatické změně

Jedním ze stěžejních nástrojů v boji proti klimatické změně by se mohlo stát ukládání oxidu uhličitého (CO₂) vyprodukovaného lidskou činností pod zem. Chytré řešení mezi úniky tohoto skleníkového plynu do atmosféry. V Česku by uložení CO₂ mělo vzniknout do roku 2024. Ambiciózní projekt byl podpořen Technologickou agenturou ČR (TA ČR) v rámci Programu KAPPA. Tentokrát čeští odborníci spojili své síly s norskými kolegy. Jejich cílem je připravit pilotní projekt ukládání CO₂ na dotovaném ložisku roty a plynu na jihovýchodní Moravě. Projekt „CO₂-SPICER“ je financovaný z Norských fondů.

Najít firmu, sehnat peníze
Vše samostatně zachytávání oxidu uhličitého představuje zhruba dvě třetiny až tři čtvrtiny nákladů, zbytek jde na dopravu a ukládání. S rozvojem počtem zařízení by se ale měla začít projevovat „účková křivka“, čímž by se míla technologie postupně zlevňovala. „Náklady na zachycení a uložení jedné tuny oxidu uhličitého se masově protoují s cenou emisí povolenek. To pak bude znamenat, že technologie začne být komerčně zajímavá“, konstatace Hladík, podle kterého také záleží na tom, o jaký zdroj oxidu jde a také kde zdroj je, respektive jak daleko se od úložišť nachází.

Příkladem v USA hovoří v optimistických předpovědích o nákladech na úroveň 40 až 50 dolarů za tunu zachyceného a uloženího plynu, v Česku předpokládáme budeme v prvních etapách na sto eurach nebo více kvůli menší přírodním podmínkám – a také než se to naučíme, připočítáme.

Česká geologická služba je nyní v kontaktu s řadou firem, které o tomto způsobu ukládání a emisí projevují zájem. V příštích týdnech by měla v Česku v rámci projektu CO₂-Spicer vzniknout „skupina zainteresovaných firem a institucí“, které by mohly využít výsledky projektu k dalšímu rozvoji technologie CCS.

Foto: tiscn.cz

CO₂ Chyť mě, když to dokážeš...

VYPUSTĚNÝ A NAVRACENÝ
Principiálně není ukládání CO₂ do podzemí žádná novinka. Už desítky let se využívá v ropném průmyslu kvůli intenzifikaci těžby. Byť samo o sobě figuruje jako vedlejší produkt. Právě zde však nejapší vznikla myšlenka dčlati to samé přímo za účelem snížení emisí. Nejprizrozenějšími úložišti se tak stala vyčizená ložiska roty či zemního plynu. Zatímco v Evropě je ukládání CO₂ vyřadné podmořskou zálež

CENA ZA „UHLÍK“
Cena emisních povolenek stoupá k dosud nepoznaným výšinám, uhlíkové náročná výroba bude v lepším případě čím dál tím dražší, v horším omezená či zastavená.

Povrchové zařízení pilotního geologického úložště CO₂ Hontomín, které se nachází v blízkosti špičkového Burgosu.
zakázání. Z akademických diskuzí o zachytávání a ukládání oxidu uhličitého se tak i na starém kontinentu stává reálná investiční příležitost a jedna z mla šan.

Schéma nosného projektu Northern Lights, který bude spuštěn v r. 2024. Zachycení

„Ukážeme, že to umíme“. Češi chtějí uložit uhlík pod zem a stát se vzorem

LUKÁŠ MAREK

VČERA 6:30

„Projekt by mohl skutečně fungovat jako vzor, že i v našem regionu jsou tyto technologie realizovatelné,“ říká v rozhovoru pro SZ vedoucí projektu přípravy pilotního podzemního úložště CO₂ Vít Hladík.

Fig. 2.9-8: Samples of articles in the media – part 2

Deviations and changes

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan; some activities even exceeded the planned extent. The only minor deviation was related to the Launch event. Due to the regulations taken by the government to overcome the coronavirus epidemic, the conference took place online instead of a physical event. The slight delay in its organisation was caused by the fact that the sister METAMORPH project was launched only in January 2021, and to keep the idea of a joint event it was necessary to wait until its consortium was ready for joining the organising committee.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R9.3	Project launch event	03/2021
R9.4	Project graphic style package	12/2020
R9.5	Updated Communication plan	11/2020
R9.6	Project information leaflet	12/2020
R9.7	Press releases	11/2020
R9.8	Project website in CZ and EN	01/2021
R9.11	Project newsletter – 1st issue	12/2021

All results listed above were enclosed with the Interim report in the ISTA system as Attachments.

2.10 WORK PACKAGE 10 – Project management and reporting

Summary

The main goal of Work Package 10 is to ensure that the project runs as smoothly as possible. The project management structure as well as the duties at the different management levels were defined with a great attention to detail already during the project preparation stage, and have been enshrined in the Project Contract and the Partnership Agreement.

Work in Work Package 10 was started at very beginning of the project in November 2020 and progressed according to the plan. The work was led by CGS (WP leader), with participation of all partners.

Task 10.1 – Project and Work Package Coordination and Management

This Task includes the management of the project and its key activities by the Project coordinator and leaders of the 10 defined Work Packages. In addition, it also covers the work of the project's three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group.

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of the project. All partners involved in the project have one representative in the General Assembly, their respective voting powers (number of votes) corresponding to the scope of the partner's involvement in the project (in person-months of work). Due to the difficult pandemic situation, the first meeting of the General Assembly was held in form of a videoconference on November 30, 2021. Minutes of the meeting are enclosed as a separate attachment with the Interim report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes.

The Management Board, supports the Project coordinator in operative project management and housekeeping duties. It is comprised of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator) and the Work Packages leaders. In addition, the representatives of Project Partners also participate in Management Board meetings to ensure smooth flow of information across the whole project team. In 2021, Management Board meetings were held regularly once a month (usually on every second Thursday of each month) in the form of teleconferences. Minutes of the 14 meetings are provided in a separate attachment to the Interim report.

The End-User Group has not been established yet, however, negotiations with potential Group participants (mostly industrial companies) were held in 2021 with promising results. The End-User Group is expected to be established in the 1st half of 2022.

Task 10.1 also covers the preparation and organisation of project meetings. During the 1st project period, two project meetings were organized, both in on-line form. The Kick-off meeting was held on November 23, 2020 and the 2nd project meeting took place on November 30, 2021. Minutes of the meetings are provided in a separate attachment. to the Interim report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes.

Task 10.1 work is organised and implemented by CGS; the participation of other Project Partners corresponds to their involvement in the management of the different Work Packages. All partners were involved in the organized project meetings.

Task 10.2 – Project Administration, Liaison with Programme Operator, Reporting

The purpose of this Task is to provide administrative support to the project management team, both during routine, day-to-day operations and in the preparation of interim reports and the final report. The Task covers also the practicalities of ongoing cooperation with the Programme Operator (TACR) and the preparation of report contents by the Project coordinator, WP leaders and Project Partners.

In 2021, the reporting activities included preparation of overview information for project monitoring by TACR and the initial phase of preparation of the 1st interim report.

Two project monitoring actions organised by TACR took place in 2021 – online Consultation on June 30 and Monitoring Visit on September 30. The reports from both actions are attached separately to the Interim report in the ISTA system.

An important part of the project administration efforts are also the public procurement procedures to accommodate the planned sub-contracts and purchases of materials and services needed by the project in full compliance with applicable regulations (in particular applicable public procurement legislation and internal procurement policies of all partners). This activity was quite limited in 2021, because no sub-contracts were prepared during this period and the purchases of material and services were carried out using the usual procedures of Project Partners.

Task 10.2 work is managed by CGS, benefitting from support of a dedicated administrative team headed by Project administrator. All Project Partners contribute to the reporting activities.

Task 10.3 – Economic and financial management of the project

Actual project costs and expenses have been tracked on ongoing, across-the-board basis and continuously compared with the approved budget. In December 2021, preparation for financial reporting within the 1st interim report was started, including relevant documents and other materials.

Task 10.3 is carried out by the Project administrator at CGS, supported by the CGS Accounting Department. All partners appointed a person responsible for regular transfers of economic data to Project administrator and provided the required input.

Deviations and changes

The only deviation from the plan was the fact that the General Assembly meeting and both project meetings were not held physically but online, due to COVID-19-related travel restrictions.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

3 INVOLVEMENT OF CONSORTIUM MEMBERS IN PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

All consortium members (Project Partners) have been actively involved in project execution from its very beginning. Their roles and responsibilities are clearly defined in the Partnership Agreement, and, in particular, in its Attachment 6 “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages”. This document specifies the work and role of each partner in every Work Package and Task in detail.

In the 1st reporting period, all Project Partners contributed to project implementation according to the plan. No major issues related to cooperation within the consortium were incurred, and the minor ones were successfully solved on the ground of the Management Board. The contributions of individual Project Partners to implementation of the work plan in individual Work Packages and Tasks are described in detail in Chapter 2.

4 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHANGES IN THE PROJECT TEAM

The total actual workload reported in the first period of CO2-SPICER is 10.81 person-years (FTE), which corresponds to 89.9 % of the plan. This figure corresponds well to the reported progress of the project and the slight deviations reported.

Key persons

MND reports two changes in key positions:

- Jiří Rez who left MND in summer 2020, i.e. after submission of project proposal, was replaced by Vladimír Opletal.
- Andrej Sučko who left MND in summer 2020, i.e. after submission of project proposal, was replaced by Petr Ořeský.

In both cases the replacements possess the same or very similar qualification and skills as the original team members.

Two persons were included in the list of key persons, following TACR requirement to specifically list PhD students and PostDocs:

- Petr Jirman (CGS), PostDoc; his original position “geochemist/modeller_1” (in the list of Other persons) was deleted in the ISTA system.
- Matěj Křístek (VSB), PhD student; his original position “support worker” (in the list of Other persons) was deleted in the ISTA system.

The actual workload of most key persons reported for the 1st project period generally corresponds to the plan. Miroslav Pereszlényi (geologist /modeller at CGS) spent less working time than planned; his work has been partly taken over by new team members working in the position of geologist (in the list of other persons). The Norwegian team members Roman Berenblyum and Anton Shchipanov spent less time than planned due to reasons explained in Chapter 6 below. MND team members Jaroslav Svoboda and Petr Ořeský have not started their work yet due to time shifts in the related Work Packages; their engagement will start in 2022.

Other persons

The CO₂-SPICER project team consists of more than 70 researchers and technicians working in five institutions. It was therefore very difficult to exactly plan the working capacity of each person / position in each year, and in many cases only estimations had to be made for the planning table. Therefore, there are slight deviations in actual working capacities in comparison with the plan at most team members; the actual figures reflect the real requirements of the project and its 10 Work Packages, and are based on the time sheets filled in by each team member. These detailed deviations per person and position are not described in the report for proportional reasons.

A few new positions were added to the list of other persons, reflecting the actual needs of project execution:

- Geologist at CGS, added to cover the increased demand of work on 3D geological modelling and partly consuming reduced capacities of geologist / modeller (key person M. Pereszlényi) and several other positions in the list of Other persons;
- Geologist / modeller at MND, added to support the extensive modelling work in WP2; the position is taken by a female researcher;
- SW specialist at GFU, added to cover unplanned requirements of programming for data transfer and data processing in Task 7.3.

Action Plan on improving the gender balance and early-stage career researchers' involvement

The Action Plan was submitted by the Project Consortium at the beginning of the project as a condition set by TACR for Project Contract signature. The implementation of the planned actions shall be reported annually to TACR within the annual project reports. The current status of implementation of the Plan is as follows:

1. *Consortium will include 10 female researchers and technicians in the project team from the beginning of the project and increase this number to 15 in the 3rd project year at the latest.*
Implementation: 14 female researchers and technicians were involved in project implementation in the 1st reporting period (7 at CGS, 4 at VSB, 1 at MND and 2 at GFU).
2. *Consortium will engage at least three early-career researchers in the solution of the project during the first project year and increase this number to five in the 3rd project year.*
Implementation: Three early-career researchers were engaged in project solution in the 1st reporting period – Petr Jirman (PostDoc) and Jakub Vácha (undergraduate student) at CGS and Matěj Krístek (PhD student) at VSB.
3. *Project Promoter CGS will appoint a young, early-career researcher as co-leader of Work Package 7 'Monitoring', starting from the beginning of the project, with the prospect of taking over the full WP leadership after gaining sufficient experience and skills, in the concrete from the start of the 3rd project year at the latest.*
Implementation: The PostDoc Petr Jirman was appointed as WP7 co-leader from the beginning of the project and, in actual fact, took over the WP leadership in full from summer 2021, with only limited support of project coordinator.

4. *Project Partner MND will engage a female researcher to act as co-leader of Work Package 2 ‘3D geological model of the storage complex’ from the beginning of the project.*

Implementation: Lenka Klímová has been acting as WP2 co-leader since the beginning of the project.

5. *Project Partner NORCE will use the established collaboration with the University of Stavanger (UiS) on supervising MSc thesis to suggest and supervise MSc topics related to CO2-SPICER activities for the students at UiS. Results of the theses will be publicly available and will contribute to increasing involvement of early career researchers and dissemination of the project results.*

Implementation: This activity has not started at NORCE yet but VSB has already launched a similar action at their university – one Bachelor, two Master and one PhD theses have been assigned for 2022 based on CO2-SPICER project activities and results (see Chapter 2.9 for details).

In general, the status of implementation of the Action Plan in the 1st project period can be considered satisfactory; good results are reported for all the five actions planned.

5 MANAGEMENT BOARD ACTIVITIES

The Management Board (corresponding to project steering committee) is the Project’s governing body responsible for operative project management. It consists of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator), all Work Package leaders and consortium partners’ representatives. In the first project period, Management Board meetings were held on a monthly basis (usually on every second Thursday of each month) in form of teleconferences.

During Management Board meetings, the progress of work in all Work Packages and other issues related to project implantation were regularly discussed. Management Board was also used as a platform for definition of cooperation actions and individual responsibilities, discussion on data hand-over, sharing of information among partners, as well as for checking the progress of actions arising from previous meetings.

Minutes of the 14 Management Board meetings held in the period 11/2020-12/2021 were uploaded to “Documents and attachments” of the 1st interim report in the ISTA system.

6 JUSTIFICATION OF THE ACTUAL COSTS INCURRED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The reported CO2-SPICER project costs of the first reporting period are 18,063,117 CZK, which corresponds to 73 % of the plan. Main reasons of the lower budget consumption are the savings in the travel cost budget caused by COVID-19-related restrictions, postponement of several large sub-contracts and lower consumption of personnel costs by partners MND and NORCE. More detailed explanations of these differences are provided below.

The main part of the incurred costs belongs to the category of personnel costs (14,572,465 CZK) that correspond to the extensive reported workload of the project team - 10.81 person-years (FTE).

The project was officially started on 1 November 2020 but the Project Contract was signed only in the beginning of 2021. Due to this fact, Project Partners GFU and VSB decided to start project research activities only in January 2021, and, hence, have not reported any costs incurred in 11-12/2020.

Project Promoter – CGS

Total costs incurred by CGS in the first reporting period were 8,409,214 CZK, which corresponds to 84.9 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 6,525,578 CZK, corresponding to 7.32 person-years (FTE) were consumed according to the plan. Planned subcontracting costs (885K CZK) were not spent due to postponement of the sub-contracts in WP6 and WP7 to 2022 (see Chapter 2.6 and 2.7 for explanation).

Only ca. 30 % of other direct costs were spent (202K CZK); the main reason is the limitation of travel due to COVID-19-related restrictions and consequent conversion of many planned project events (Launch event, project meetings, WP and Task meetings) to online mode. Main cost items in this category are:

- Inland travel costs (15K CZK), mainly to Zar-3 site for field survey, and to Hodonín and Ostrava for meetings with Project Partners.
- Conference fees and international travel costs (47K CZK) related to presentation of the project and its results at three international conferences (WP9) and project coordinator's visit to the Norwegian partner.
- Services, repair & maintenance of laboratory equipment in WP5 (19K CZK)
- Spare parts for instruments and consumables in WP5 (67K CZK)
- Spare parts for monitoring instruments, consumables for field work, batteries, chemicals, etc. in WP7 (42K CZK)
- Miscellaneous small office consumables in WP10 (12K CZK)

Project Partner MND

Total costs incurred by MND in the first reporting period were 2,514,048 CZK, which corresponds to 54.5 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 1,727,343 CZK, corresponding to 1.49 person-years (FTE) were consumed. This is only 48.4 % of the planned amount. There are several reasons for this relatively low figure.

- The changes in MND project team (see Chapter 4) brought engagement of new team members holding more junior positions in the company with significantly lower salaries compared to the original team members.
- The planned personnel unit costs were overestimated due to lack of experience at MND with planning and budgeting of research projects. Due to this, external rates were used for the budget instead of pure personnel cost-based figures. These external rates included, e.g., a share of the SW maintenance costs of the SW used by the personnel. This has now been corrected in the cost statement, and the SW maintenance costs were reported correctly among Other direct costs. As a result, the reported personnel costs are lower than planned.
- MND have spent slightly less working capacity in the first project period than planned (1.68 person-years).

Other direct costs (284K CZK) correspond solely to SW maintenance costs, calculated according to the percentage of the use of particular SW modules for the project. These costs are higher than the planned amount due to the reasons explained above. No travel costs were consumed due to conversion of project actions to online mode.

Project Partner NORCE

Total costs incurred by NORCE in the first reporting period were 5,439,700 CZK, which corresponds to 66.0 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 5,395,800 CZK, corresponding to 0.74 person-years (FTE) were consumed. This is only 66.5 % of the planned amount. The reasons for this lower cost consumption are mainly the slightly delayed and partly limited engagement of NORCE researchers in some Work Packages (especially WP2 and WP4), caused by delayed delivery of input data as a consequence of COVID-19-related restrictions (e.g. delayed signature of the Non-disclosure Agreement, impossibility to travel to Czechia for project meetings, etc.) and the damages in the MND core repository caused by tornado in June 2021 (see Chapter 7 for more details).

Only ca. 34 % (44K CZK) of planned other direct costs were spent; the main reason is the limitation of travel due to COVID-19-related restrictions and consequent savings of travel costs. The main cost items in this category are:

- Travel costs (25.5K CZK) to internal team meetings (Stavanger – Bergen)
- Shipment of ultrasonic velocity tool-box (used in WP4) to Ostrava (18.5K CZK)

Project Partner VSB

Total costs incurred by VSB in the first reporting period were 939,311 CZK, which corresponds to 100 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 526,453 CZK, corresponding to 0.63 person-years (FTE) were consumed according to the plan.

Other direct costs consumption (225K CZK) was consistent with the plan. Main cost items in this category are:

- Travel costs (14K CZK), mostly to the MND core repository at Lužice (core inspections and sampling) and to the Zar-3 field (field surveys)
- Machine calibration, service maintenance in WP4 and WP5 (11K CZK)
- Consumables - mainly laboratory material for tests and experiments in WP4 and WP5, tenzometres, oil, core bits for drilling of samples, grinding and cutting wheels for WP4 and WP5, material necessary for preparation of samples and equipment modification (196K CZK)
- Miscellaneous small office consumables (4K CZK)

Project Partner GFU

Total costs incurred by GFU in the first reporting period were 760,845 CZK, which corresponds to 74.5 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 397,290 CZK, corresponding to 0.63 person-years (FTE) were slightly higher than planned. The reason for this minor deviation is the additional work on seismic data transfer programming and the unplanned additional work related to the deployment of a temporal seismic array at Zar-3 with the aim to monitor the water injection test (see Chapter 2.7, Task 2.3 for details).

The planned sub-contracting budget (ca. 275K CZK) was not consumed. It was planned to cover the delivery and installation of seismic monitoring stations. This activity was realised, at a lower cost (198,440 CZK) but the slightly different character of the delivery (special cases for seismic stations) did not correspond to the definition of a sub-contract according to TACR guidelines (service of research nature). Due to this, and also in compliance with accounting standards and usual practice used at GFU, this cost item was included in the category of Other direct costs.

Other direct costs consumption (282K CZK) was slightly lower than the plan, mainly due to COVID-19-related travel limitations and corresponding savings of travel costs. Main cost items in this category are:

- Delivery of special cases for seismic stations (198K CZK - see above)
- Travel costs (14K CZK) to Zar-3 site for field work
- Material and consumables for field work, software (62K CZK)
- Services, SW licence (8K CZK)

7 OBSTACLES DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The COVID-19 pandemic situation and related governmental orders, restricting common live and work, represented the main issue during the first project period (2020 - 2021). Due to travel restriction (both local and international) and limited number of persons allowed to sit in one room, all project events and meetings had to be organized online only. This goes for the project Launch event, two planned face-to-face project meetings, as well as most Work Package and Task meetings.

While the online contact fulfilled all necessary requirements from the point of view of data and information sharing and exchange, personal contact and face-to-face discussions were missing. This slowed down the involvement of Norwegian colleagues into the work in some Work Packages, especially WP2. Moreover, the obstacles related to COVID-19 caused some delays in some parts of the project. E.g., the transfer of site-specific confidential data from MND was delayed by a few weeks due to problems with signing the Non-disclosure Agreement by statutory representatives of Consortium partners during the pandemic lockdown in the beginning of 2021. The deployment of seismic monitoring stations at Zar-3 was also delayed due to COVID-related travel restrictions.

The above-mentioned issues influenced the budget consumption in the first project period - the planned travel costs were largely underspent, and the expenditures of NORCE, including personnel costs, were lower than planned.

Another obstacle influencing the project was the tornado that hit South-Eastern Moravia in June 2021. The tornado destroyed the MND premises at Lužice, including the building of the drilling core repository and the laboratories (see Fig. 7-1). The core repository is still inaccessible due to reconstruction, and the next selection of suitable cores, needed for additional geomechanical and geochemical experiments, is currently impossible. This will influence the time plan of WPs 4 and 5 and will probably cause some delays in project execution in 2022. It is expected that the core repository will be accessible again in early 2022.

Fig. 7-1: Destroyed MND premises at Lužice after the tornado in June 2021.

8 SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT FOR THE PURPOSE OF PUBLICATION BY THE PROGRAMME OPERATOR

The Czech-Norwegian project CO₂-SPICER, focusing on preparation of the first pilot geological storage site in the Czech Republic, has successfully finished the first year of implementation. In the beginning, the focus was on collation of all accessible input data, their verification and consolidation. This step was followed by construction of a 3D geological model of the storage complex - the main activity of this project phase. Moreover, a detailed study of geomechanical and geochemical properties of rocks building the reservoir and its overburden has been started, as well as testing of usability of various methods for long-term monitoring of the stored CO₂.

Czech version

Česko-norský projekt CO₂-SPICER, zaměřený na přípravu prvního pilotního geologického úložiště CO₂ v ČR, právě uzavřel úspěšný první rok řešení. Na samém začátku bylo středem pozornosti shromáždění veškerých dostupných vstupních dat, jejich prověření a setřídění. Na tento krok pak navázaly práce na konstrukci trojrozměrného geologického modelu úložného komplexu, což je stěžejní aktivita této fáze projektu. Bylo rovněž zahájeno podrobné studium geomechanických a geochemických vlastností hornin tvořících úložiště a jeho nadložní těsnění a ověřování použitelnosti různých monitorovacích metod pro dlouhodobé sledování uloženého CO₂.

9 CONCLUSION

The work in the first project period of CO₂-SPICER was performed according to the plan, with only minor deviations. All results planned for the period were delivered.

Good progress has been made towards achievement of all specific project objectives:

- A significant part of work on construction of the 3D geological model of the storage complex was completed in WP2.
- Initial preparatory steps for dynamic modelling of reservoir behaviour were done in WP3.
- Assessment of geomechanical and geochemical properties of reservoir rocks and caprock is ongoing; laboratory tests and experiments on core samples are being performed within WP4 and WP5.
- First part of the risk assessment work was completed in WP6.
- Assessment of suitability of various monitoring methods for the project site and first field campaigns of baseline monitoring were completed in WP7, both representing important input in the site monitoring plan preparation.
- Initial information and data for preparation of scenarios of storage site development have been collected in WP8.
- Czech-Norwegian cooperation in the area of CCS was fostered not only through intense mutual cooperation between Czech and Norwegian partners of project consortium, but also through liaison with other Czech-Norwegian projects funded from EEA/Norway Grants, as well as with the Norwegian Embassy in Prague.

In summary, the achievements of the 1st project period represent a good basis for successful continuation of the project and reaching all its planned goals.

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More information about the project can be found at
CO2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

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